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Evaluation of the Fisher Effect within an Emerging Markets Framework

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MSc(Econ) International Economics, Banking and Finance

Stock Returns and Inflation.

Evaluation of The Fisher Effect within an Emerging Markets Framework.

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I would like to devote this piece of work to my Parents Georgios and Dimitra Asimomyti for their unlimited provision of tangible and more importantly, intangible support throughout my studies and further.

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Declaration

I hereby confirm the following:

- *This work has not previously been accepted in substance for any degree and is not being concurrently submitted in candidature for any other degree.*

- *This dissertation is being submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the degree of MSc (Econ) International Economics, Banking and Finance awarded by Cardiff University.*

- *This dissertation is the result of my own independent work/investigation, except where otherwise stated. Other sources are acknowledged in the references and bibliography section.*

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Date

Abstract

The topic we are challenged to analyze is the relationship between inflation and equity returns. It has been a very controversial topic since, as we are about to examine the empirical evidence provided by empiricists and academics throughout the world and for different samples and periods has been very conflicting. In more detail there have been all possible outcomes in the relationship between inflation and equity returns. Some researchers have established that there exists a positive relationship between inflation and equity returns while others have found a negative one. If we decide to introduce more complexity to the issue then we find that the outcome has also been controversial in terms of different samples and more importantly in terms of time horizons. For different portfolios the relationship has been either positive or negative. All the above imply a very sticking result, as we will see since economic theory steaming back from the 1930's is very strict for the relationship between the two variables.

In this essay we will introduce the pure economic, financial theory related to the issue and we will be also examining the empirical evidence found in the literature. Finally we will apply the theory in terms of an emerging countries framework. Utilizing simple and more advanced econometric techniques we will attempt to establish whether there exists a relationship between stock returns and inflation as the one suggested by Irvine Fisher.

Chapter I

1.1 Introduction

The theory that was first introduced by J.M. Keynes that the stock markets are characterized by the irrational aspects of the market behavior seems to collapse, since everyday we observe share prices being driven by extremely volatile expectations. Fundamental analysis or intrinsic value theory has been very successful since it is viewing share pricing as the result of decisions made by rational and highly informed individuals. Fundamentals of course include inflation which has been one of the most commonly included variables in the analysis of fundamentalists fund managers and academics.

It is now taken as a stylized fact- by market participants and academics alike- that returns on stocks suffer significantly in the face of high and more importantly for our analysis rising inflation. As we are about to examine and discuss in the next sections this comes in contrast with the state of conventional wisdom and pure economic theory of less than three decades ago. What we have all learned while pursuing an undergraduate course in Finance is that shares represent a good and probably the best hedge against inflation. On the other side mainly the Wall-Street and City gurus argue that the fantastic returns we have been enjoying for the last twenty years come naturally as a result of the decline on inflationary pressures and expectations. This is shown, captured on tests tracked on the persistent historical relationship between inflation and price-earnings ratios. Nevertheless academics are still puzzled from the fact that the empirical evidence is in contrast to the strongly established economic theory. We will outline some striking examples of recent short and long-term evidence that shows that shares are negatively hit from inflation and expected

inflation. The significance of expected and unexpected inflationary pressures or indeed deflation can be captivated utilizing some recent examples of monetary policy conducting from some major central banks. It was only recently that the FED and its chairman Alan Greenspan decided to increase the U.S base rate by 20 basis points. Just before and during the official announcement and within an efficient market hypothesis framework we observed the major stock exchange indices like the Dow Jones Industrial Average, S&P 500, Nasdaq, DAX and FTSE-100 being under pressure. Investors throughout the world have been liquidating part of their portfolios and opening new positions in the bonds market. As a result the 30 years US Treasury benchmark bond price has been moving upwards thereby reducing it's yield. This is only a very rough example of the implications of inflation -and in more detail expected inflation- within an asset allocation framework.

Utilizing another long horizon example we can remind ourselves that from the mid 1970's onwards, globally we have experienced the adoption of large-scale deflationary policies. The Peak was during the 80's when the monetary experiment took place with Margaret Thatcher in the UK and Ronald Reagan in the US. This is important to our analysis since for the past 25 years we have also experienced an unprecedented growth in equity prices coming to our days where we observe the Dow Jones in excess of 11000 points and the FTSE-100 around 7000 points. Other very prominent examples are the Equity markets in Portugal, Greece and Spain. These were economies characterized traditionally by high inflation, but since the adoption of the convergence programs with the end purpose becoming members of the EMU we have observed that in concurrence with the fall in inflation we have also experienced a growth in the value of equity claims.

1.2 Intrinsic Value Equity Pricing

Path breaking, highly influential research by Irving Fisher during the 1930's set the cornerstone of a new financial framework both in academia and in practice. Irving Fisher has been arguing and insisting that the value of financial assets at any point in time depended solely on the discounted sum of their future cash flows to the holder. Utilizing an example of this kind of approach for the determination of equities/bonds prices, the appropriate future income streams are, the cash dividends/coupon and the later sales price/ "bubble" payment.

Let us now examine in more detail how can someone price, value equity claims using

A "Fisherian" approach of discounting future inflows.

Buying a share essentially means two things. Firstly the investor will enjoy a regular payment in the form of dividend, which in most cases is optional and secondly the owner of the asset will receive a lump sum- in cases of profit- of money on top of the buying price in case he decides to sell the share. As we can see so far there are no significant differences between shares and other financial assets such as bonds. The only difference so far is the uncertainty in the timing and the amounts received in the case of shares- this is of course the reason that shares enjoy higher returns in most cases-. We can summarize all the above in the form of the equation below:

$$P_S = P_V = D_1/(1+r) + \sum D_i^x/(1+r)^i + P_n^x/(1+r)^n$$

P_S : Current Market price of share

P_n^x : Price expected to be sold

D_1 : Dividend to be received in the present time period

D_i^x : Dividend to be received in the i^{th} period ($2 < i < n$)

This can be described as a typical “Fisherian” approach towards valuing financial assets.

Let us now ask the questions how can we:

- Obtain estimates of expected future dividends and
- What is the appropriate rate at which we should discount future earnings?

The first question, which is linked to the expected future dividends, is related to the growth potential of the firm and the so-called payout ratio, which is the amount of the profits paid out in the form of dividends. There are many factors affecting the payout ratio and their analysis is currently beyond our scope.

As for the rate that we should discount the future earnings of the firm this is obviously related to the interest rate available on long term bonds. Long term bonds are used for discounting the cash inflows because an equity claim has no “expiration date” Such bonds are for example the U.S. Treasury Benchmark bonds such as the 30 year one. An important issue we should raise here is that we do not postulate that the two rates should be the same, after all this fundamentally cannot be true, we only suggest that the bond rate should be the anchor of the discount rate plus of course a premium which indicates the riskiness of the share in accordance for example with the Capital Asset Pricing Model and the Mean-Variance model.

In other words we have reached the conclusion that interest rates are highly important for pricing equity claims- keeping in mind that in any case this cannot be itself the only influential factor-. This in turn is leading us to the conclusion that monetary policy can be a very important factor for pricing shares. This conclusion has already been illustrated in the introductory part with the utilization of the example of the recent FED actions. Central Banks therefore can play a very

significant role for the stock markets around the world since with their surprise movements can cause disturbances in the allocation of portfolios. We mention surprise movements because we have assumed that economic agents are rational. In other words everything already known for the current or future monetary policy has already been incorporated, discounted in the current prices. Therefore only an unexpected, unanticipated change in the monetary policy will cause any effects. What in essence we are implying here is that the assumption of Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) holds at any moment.

Having discussed the notion of nominal interest rates and their relevance for pricing equity claims let us now introduce the so called Fisher Hypothesis introduced by Irving Fisher in the 1930's in it's original form and we will continue by adjusting it in the inflation-equity returns framework for our analysis.

1.3 Irving Fisher's Expectations and the Fisher-Williams model

Fisher has been described numerous times as the man who fundamentally invented finance, as we know it today. Fisher introduced many of the theories widely used today from practitioners in the 1930's. Let us now introduce the most important ones and the ones that are directly linked to our issue

Fisher is also responsible for introducing expectations in the science of Economics. In more detail he hypothesized that the nominal rate of interest is equal to the sum of a real purchasing power adjusted rate augmented by the expected rate of inflation¹. The theory outlined above can be captured from the equation provided below:

¹ *Appreciation and interest. Publications of the American Economics Association. Third Series August 1896, and the rate of interest (1907).*

$$r_t = m + a_1 E_t P_{t+1}^e + u_t$$

But the theory that truly gave Fisher- in combination with the one above- the right to be remembered as the Adam Smith of Finance is the classical equilibrium model

(Or Fisher-William model) described below²:

The optimal scale of investment, borrowing and saving of each economic agent at any time in the economy is simultaneously determined under idealized conditions

(No uncertainty, transactions costs, market imperfections and asymmetries) by a set of interest rates which reflects- and by definition varies- the initial endowments, earned income streams, real investment opportunities and preference functions of each of the agents that participates in the marketplace. It is very understandable and obvious why Fisher was considered to be one of the earliest monetarists since he is very clearly dividing the real and the monetary sectors of the economy into two completely unrelated sectors, something that today as we know can only be described as fallacy.

Someone might ask at this point the question:” Why does Fisher never consider Risk and uncertainty?” The answer to the question is that he would have had probably included them in his analysis if the appropriate tools for the analysis of uncertainty and risk were known at the time³. We are about to introduce why the Classical theory is concerning us in relation to the inflation-equity yields framework. But let us first discuss the principal statement that will be the starting point of our analysis. We should also point out that there exist many variations of the Fisher Model but nevertheless we will concentrate here to most common one namely.

² *The rate of Interest (1907) and The Theory of Interest (1930).*

³ *John Lintner , Inflation and Security Returns, Journal of Finance Vol. XXX, No 2, May 1975,*

“Expected nominal rates of return on financial assets move one-to-one with expected inflation.”

Fisher’s source of inspiration was the investigation of the Gibson Paradox he pursued. The Gibson Paradox is a phenomenon originally noticed by J.M. Keynes in the 1930’s but was named by Keynes for Gibson. Keynes observed that in long-term studies of the US and the UK economy the interest rates were positively correlated to the price level. Of course this is in contradiction to the Classical Monetary Theory, which is consistent to the view that interest rates ought to be independent to the price level.

Let us remind ourselves that the classical theory introduced by Fisher is making clear that only the real endowments are affecting the real interest rates and vice versa. Following this statement we can move further and state that the real returns to the ownership of capital goods be invariant to the general price level, since these returns are already determined by the real sector, input-output relations and factors of production proportions. In conclusion to this we can further expand our thinking and realize that if real returns are completely invariant to inflation then the real present value of real returns should also be unaffected by current inflation or even future expected inflation.

Money values then should, will vary in accordance, proportion to the general price level. This implies that nominal capital gains on unlevered equity are equal to the rate of inflation, thereby reaching the starting point which states that inflation and equity returns should move one-to-one with expected inflation.

The above theory can be and it is often formulated as ex-ante real rates being statistically uncorrelated with expected inflation. One additional assumption often

employed by researchers linked to the theory is that the ex-ante real rate is constant. This kind of approach was first introduced by Eugene Fama work on interest rates as short-term predictors of inflation. In any case the Fisher model is expected to hold for all assets and over all time horizons such that:

$$\sum_{i=1}^J R_{t+1} = \mathbf{a}_j + \mathbf{b}_x E \left[\sum_{i=1}^j \mathbf{p}_{t+1} | \mathbf{f}_t \right] + \mathbf{e}_t(j)$$

With $H_0: \hat{a}_j=1$, where R_t is the continuously compounded nominal return on an asset, δ_t is the continuously compounded rate of inflation, \bar{o}_t is the agent's information set and \hat{a} captures the prediction error of the nominal rate. For one asset then the model can be described as:

$$R_{t+1} = \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{b}E(\mathbf{p}_{t+1} | \mathbf{f}_t) + \mathbf{e}_t$$

The regression models described above estimate the conditional to the information set \bar{o} expected value of the stock market return as a function of the expected inflation rate. Therefore, an estimate of \hat{a} , which is statistically indistinguishable from unity, is consistent with the hypothesis that the expected nominal return on common stocks varies in one to one correspondence with the expected inflation rate, and this of course can be discounted as that stocks provide a complete, perfect hedge against expected inflationary pressures.

1.4 Criticism and limitations of the Classical Model.

We have already mentioned that the Fisher Classical model seems not to capture or explain the empirical evidence and we will get into more detail for this when we will be examining the literature on the subject. For this section we will be examining any theoretical limitations, criticism the model has been through.

In the case of rising inflation the adjustments that are necessary to be taken include rising labor, material and other costs. Under the insistence of utilizing FIFO- First In First Out- and the historical rather, than the replacement cost depreciation accounting techniques might be fatal for the maintenance of the pre-inflation rise profit margins. So the adjustments for the after inflation rise are incomplete and cannot justify the Fisher effect, they rather justify that since the profit margins- and the price of the share is the discounted present value of the future profits- will be reduced there should be a negative relationship between inflation and equity returns. In more detail if we assume that the numerator- of the equity pricing formula- that represents the dividends is becoming smaller and, or the denominator, which includes the nominal long-term interest rate, plus the risk premium has become larger, then it follows that the negative relationship between inflation and equity returns is absolutely justified.

Let us now for a moment assume that those accounting techniques are abandoned and LIFO- Last In First Out- and replacement cost depreciation techniques are used by the finance managers, for the sake of argument we can assume that there is perfect adjustment to the rising costs due to the inflationary pressures, will there still be any discrepancies?

The answer is Yes, even in this case where the profit margins remain unaffected from the increased costs the firm's dependence upon external financing will be necessarily higher- no matter the accounting techniques or the current capital structure of the firm-

, the higher the rate of inflation, unexpected or even expected. Moreover this greater dependence on outside financing which stems as a result of the increase in inflation will have an effect –negative of-course- in the outstanding equity claims, which of-course by definition implies that the real returns on equity will be adversely affected. The results hold even if new equity or added debt is issued in order for the firm to manage and maintain the growth potentials that enjoyed before the rise of the inflation in the case of foreseeing inflationary pressures. The reason is simple, if the new equity issue takes place after the realization of the inflation rise, it is implied that the discount factor that the potential equity holders will be discounting the new issue will be definitely greater for a given dependence for external financing. On the other hand if the same thing happens and instead of equity, debt is the instrument no further analysis is necessary, the cost of funding will be higher since the nominal rate of interest will be higher. We can also go further and establish that the value of a highly leveraged firm will be naturally less than it used to be due to higher default risk. The above analysis can be accurately described as re-statements of the Modigliani- Miller propositions.

1.5 Empirical Evidence of the relationship Inflation, Equity Returns.

A very important piece of work on our topic was the one from Fama and Schwert published in the Journal of Financial Economics in 1977. In this paper they have been examining the performance of various assets as a hedge against inflation. The examined period is 1953 to 1971, which was a highly inflationary period so their findings are of significance importance. They use US data and in particular the Consumer Price Index (CPI) to estimate the rate of inflation. The purpose of that was originally introduced by Irving Fisher- (1930, ch. I)- who argued that the end purpose

of investment is eventually consumption thus it is sensible to use the inflation rate for consumption goods. For the equity returns they use data taken from the New York Stock Exchange (NYSE). They also regress inflation with U.S. Treasury bills and bonds. It should be pointed out that they are examining empirical evidence for the performance of various assets as hedge instruments against expected and unexpected, surprise inflation. They found that the U.S. Treasury bonds and bills provide a perfect hedge for inflation for the 1953-71 period. They also examined labor income and they found there is a little short-term relationship with either expected or unexpected inflation. What they describe as anomalous, at the time, is the fact that they find evidence that common stocks were completely negatively related to the expected component of inflation, and probably also to the unexpected. It should also be pointed out that their research was pursued on a monthly, quarterly and semiannually basis. On their explanation for the anomalous findings for the relationship between common stocks returns and inflation they provide the following.

They state that tax and accounting reasons might be the reason as they have been outlined previously and introduced by Lintner in 1975. They also put the hypothesis put forward by Kessel in 1956, which states that unanticipated inflation is to the benefit of the stockholders of firms that are net debtors. Let us say at this point that the coefficients of their research were statistically insignificant with the adjusted for degree of freedoms R^2 standing at 0.03.

Zvi Bodie in his paper "Common stocks as a hedge against inflation" is utilizing annual, quarterly and monthly data for a twenty years period – 1953-72- conclude that there exists an illusion among economists in the form that the return of common stocks is positively correlated to inflation. He argues that in fact the case is completely the opposite. Inflation and stock returns are negatively correlated to both

expected and unexpected inflation both in the short and in the long run with stronger evidence for the short run. Bodie concludes and suggests that investment policy aiming to immunize a stocks portfolio against inflation is short selling. These were very disturbing results -at the time- for standard economic theory as was introduced by Irving Fisher and others at later times. Bruno Solnik has been one of the frontrunners in examining the performance of stocks against inflation. In his paper “The Relation between Stock Prices and Inflationary Expectations: The International Evidence” he examines a sample from nine countries, over a very important for inflation period. The sample used covers the period 1971-80 a period, which was highlighted by, repeated oil shocks, which yielded inflationary pressures globally. This time inflation was captured utilizing interest rates as a proxy variable. His research was very important for the Fisher effect since the data used were all from the major markets in the world with more than 85% of the global capitalization. He concludes that the “Fisherian” assumption that real returns are independent of inflationary expectations is soundly rejected for all the countries included in his sample. On the other hand it is very evidently supported the fact that there is a negative correlation between inflation and equity returns. He also checks whether his decision of using interest rates, as proxy variable for inflation is not in any case problematic for the analysis by testing a real interest rate effect. His conclusion finally gives rise to revisions on expectations. Let us not forget here that the results outlined above are very surprising given the fact that equity claims represent claims against real assets, from this point of view common stocks should be a good hedge against inflationary pressures. Exactly this point is outlined and emphasized by Gautam Kaul. Kaul has examined post world war II data from the US, Canada, U.K. and finally Germany. Kaul accepted the fact that there is a negative relationship between stock

returns and inflation but he decided to test the Proxy Hypothesis in order to determine the reasons that this relationship is so strong against the fallacy of the Fisher Effect. He tests the so-called Fama Proxy Hypothesis as was described in a previous section. The countries above were selected since the author argues that they have highly developed industrialized economies with well-developed capital markets and secondly because the relevant data were available for the chosen period. The methodology that he is using to approach inflation is the one followed by Fama and Gibbons in 1984. He extracts the inflation rate from the Treasury bill rates assuming that the expected real returns follow a random walk. Again the research is pursued under monthly, quarterly and annual data. As we have already mentioned the Proxy Hypothesis relies on two major links:

1. The positive relation between stock returns and future real activity.
2. The negative relationship between inflation and real activity.

He concludes that the negative inflation-real activity relations, reinforced by counter-cyclical monetary responses, explain the negative relations between stock returns and inflation witnessed in the post war period.

The following piece of work is somehow distinctive. Rober B. Barsky in his paper “The Fisher Hypothesis and the Forecastability and Persistence of Inflation” attempts to explain why Fisher in a sense was not wrong. One of the purposes of the paper is to attempt to show why the pre 1960’s data look more Fisherian in the sense of displaying a higher correlation between short-term nominal interest rates and measured inflation of proxies for expected inflation. In his conclusion he reports that it is very important to distinguish between the degree of correlation between nominal interest rates and realized inflation and secondly the relationship between expected inflation and expected real rates. Jacob Budoukh and Matthew Richardson of Stern

School of Business, NY University in defense of the Fisher model which they characterize as “one of the most respected” financial models decide to pursue a long-run research on the issue, than an “unfair” short-run which was the case for the previous research. Nevertheless they state -as we do also in a previous section- that normally the Fisher effect should be expected to hold at all horizon, while we have seen that this is not true at least in the short run. They use data that cover almost two centuries from 1802 to 1990. We understand that due to the fact of the various sources of such a long data the dataset may not be very homogenous and this was the first difficulty of the research. They cover both the U.K. and the U.S. market and their results are of great significance since they imply something that might be of great importance. Nominal stock returns over a long horizon are positively correlated to both actual and expected inflation. In effect what they say is that the Fisher effect holds for horizons of 5 or more years. This is a sticking result since it proves that there might be a case for a Fisher effect in longer horizon framework. We should point out here that the researchers utilized an instrumental variable approach; a problem that arose is the fact that they had quite large standard errors. Another similar result was the one by Gultekin in 1983. Gultekin studied 25 countries from 1947-79 and found a cross-sectional slope of the Fisher model of 0.79 and a standard error of 0.27 with an R^2 of 28%. Solnik and Solnik argue that the empirical evidence suffers from the fact that inflation is a slow moving adaptive process with low variance compared to the variance of the returns. Again we see that the support for the Fisher model comes from long-horizon returns in this case 32 years. The conclusion is that for short time horizons and/or utilization of the Fama Proxy Hypothesis is giving a negative relationship between stock prices and revisions in expected inflation Following the same approach Solnik and Solnik decided to test the model utilizing

multi-country data for holding period horizons of 1 to 12 months and longer horizons jointly. Their dataset is from 1958-1996 and includes all the major markets representing 85% of the global capitalization. They do not reject the Fisher effect for any horizon and they also contrast the Boudoukh and Richardson who find that the Fisher effect should be rejected for holding periods 1 to 12 months. This is in addition to the fact that the Fisher model also holds for longer horizons. Their standard errors also are a lot smaller than Boudoukh and Richardson. A possible explanation that Solnik and Solnik provide for their findings is that the predictive capabilities of the instruments used from Boudoukh and Richardson are far less predictive for the US inflation, contrary to the database used by Solnik and Solnik, which is multi-country, and is far better predictive.

We can see that the Fisher effect and variations such as the Proxy Hypothesis has been tested very extensively over very long period samples and for different countries. The results are very controversial since they don't provide us with any insight as to whether the Fisher effect holds. Others find that such thing as the Fisher effect doesn't truly exist, while others find support only for longer-period horizons. On the other hand we have Solnik and Solnik who have found empirical evidence suggesting that the Fisher effect exists strongly both for longer and shorter time horizons.

1.5 Conclusion

We have seen that the model has been a highly controversial one since the empirical evidence is highly contradictory. The very striking conclusion is that the Fisher effect although is supposed to hold at any moment and within any time horizon the empirical evidence from the literature review shows that it might hold or not depending the time horizon. In the next section we will utilize the simple OLS with which we will attempt to establish our own conclusions based on a dataset taken from representative emerging markets.

Chapter II

2.1 Introduction to Empirical Analysis.

As mentioned in earlier parts this essay is concerned with a re-examination of the Fisher effect in a very recent sample consisted by representative developing, emerging markets. It is in other words an examination of the Fisher effect in terms of an emerging countries framework. We have aimed to produce a globally diversified portfolio of data and as such we have chosen countries from the Central and South America, Europe and Asia. The countries are Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Mexico from South and Central America, Czech Republic, Greece, Poland, Hungary, Portugal and Israel from Europe and finally Indonesia and Philippines. Our sample spans from January 1993 to June 1999 and it is monthly. Our data include the stock index the 15th of every month for each country, the Consumer Price Index (CPI) for each month. The data were taken from DataStream and were taken from the International Monetary Fund (IMF) database. The CPI Index is used as a measure of expected inflation from past inflation rates. We will begin the analysis by outlining our Ordinary Least Squares results for every country and by determining the significance of the results.

2.2 Empirical Evidence of the Fisher Effect

For this part we will be utilizing the simple OLS analysis in order to examine the Fisher effect as it has been pursued in the vast majority of the literature. The relationship we are regressing is the one outlined below :

$$R_{t+1} = \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{bE}(\mathbf{p}_{t+1} | \mathbf{f}_t) + \mathbf{e}_t$$

We are modeling the stock returns as the monthly percentage change of the index-

$$R_t = \frac{S_t - S_{(t-1)}}{S_{(t-1)}} \times 100$$

While expected inflation is modeled as was suggested by Gutelkin, the monthly percentage change of the Consumer's Price Index- CPI-.

$$\mathbf{p}_{t+1} = \frac{CPI_t - CPI_{(t-1)}}{CPI_{(t-1)}} \times 100$$

We have already reported in a previous part why we have chosen to use the CPI as a proxy to inflation, just to remind to ourselves this is in line with Fisher's explanation of what will agents do with the extra returns they will receive in case of potential inflationary pressures. The results, tests and implementation for each country are provided below and the full output tables are provided in the Appendix.

Argentina

For Argentina the sample used is monthly and it spans from September 1993 to June of 1999. We can see in the result below-table 1- that there is no strong support for the Fisher effect. In fact we can state the opposite since there is shown a rather insignificant but nevertheless negative relationship.

Table 1

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Argentina			

Dependent variable is RS			
70 observations used for estimation from September 1993 to June 1999			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.012195	.014343	.85029[.398]
INFL	-.038402	.039100	-.98216[.330]

R-Squared	.013987	R-Bar-Squared	-.5128E-3
S.E. of Regression	.11564	F-stat. F(1, 68)	.96464[.330]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.0084350	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.11561
Residual Sum of Squares	.90941	Equation Log-likelihood	52.6953
Akaike Info. Criterion	50.6953	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	48.4468
DW-statistic		2.0323	

$$R_e = 0.12195(0.014343) - .038402(0.0391)\delta_i$$

Nevertheless we can see that our results cannot be considered significant and more importantly the R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at 0.014 and -0.000512 respectively. In the parentheses we can see the standard errors. If we expected a strong support for the Fisher effect we should have had a p_i coefficient approximately 1 which would capture the one for one relationship as it has been suggested by Fisher. And of course we should have had definitely higher values for the R^2 values. We can see that the results cannot yield any insights into our analysis since are not significant.

Brazil

For Brazil our sample is from November 1994 to May 1999. The results of the OLS regression are provided below-Table 2- :

Table 2

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Brazil			

Dependent variable is RS			
55 observations used for estimation from November 1994 to May 1999			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.0081842	.024042	.34041[.735]
INFL	.018784	.021934	.85637[.396]

R-Squared	.013648	R-Bar-Squared	-.0049622
S.E. of Regression	.12204	F-stat. F(1, 53)	.73337[.396]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.023194	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.12174
Residual Sum of Squares	.78942	Equation Log-likelihood	38.6626
Akaike Info. Criterion	36.6626	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	34.6553
DW-statistic		2.2272	

$$R_i = 0.0081842(.024042) + .018784(.021934)p_i$$

In this case we don't have a negative beta coefficient nevertheless statistically is not far from zero. Again we see no support evidence for the Fisher effect whatsoever. the R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at 0.013648 and -0.0049622 respectively. The R^2 values are extremely low again.

Chile

The sample for Chile is from February 1994 to May 1999. In the case of Chile the

OLS analysis gave the results in the table -table 3- outlined below :

Table 3

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Chile			

Dependent variable is RS			
64 observations used for estimation from February 1994 to May 1999			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.0017288	.013927	.12413[.902]
INFL	-.7024E-3	.022435	-.031310[.975]

R-Squared	.1581E-4	R-Bar-Squared	-.016113
S.E. of Regression	.061009	F-stat. F(1, 62)	.9803E-3[.975]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.0013639	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.060523
Residual Sum of Squares	.23077	Equation Log-likelihood	89.1953
Akaike Info. Criterion	87.1953	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	85.0364
	DW-statistic		1.8476

$$R_i = 0.0017288(0.013927) - 0.0007024(0.022435)p_i$$

In the case of Chile again we find a beta coefficient of almost zero. R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at 0.000015 and -0.016 respectively. The R^2 values are extremely low again. They cannot give us any explanatory power. So far the Fisher effect is absolutely not supported by the empirical evidence. The t-ratios of the coefficients are very small and the coefficients themselves are not statistically significant just like in all previous cases.

Czech Republic

The case of the Czech Republic is outlined below and it is of extreme importance, since it is considered to be at the time the most developed market of the former Eastern Europe block. Our dataset is from May 1994 to June of 1999. The OLS regression results are given in the table –table 4– below:

Table 4

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Czech Republic			

Dependent variable is RS			
62 observations used for estimation from May 1994 to June 1999			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	-.0030471	.012738	-.23921[.812]
INFL	-.0039795	.012989	-.30636[.760]

R-Squared	.0015618	R-Bar-Squared	-.015079
S.E. of Regression	.076436	F-stat. F(1, 60)	.093856[.760]
Mean of Dependent Variable	-.0055737	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.075866
Residual Sum of Squares	.35055	Equation Log-likelihood	72.4631
Akaike Info. Criterion	70.4631	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	68.3360
	DW-statistic		1.6258

$$R_i = -0.030470(0.012738) - 0.0039795(0.012989)p_i$$

R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at 0.0015618 and -0.015079 respectively. Again the coefficients are almost equal to zero and the results are not statistically significant- the t-ratios are extremely low-. In this case too there is no such thing as Fisher effect.

Greece

The case of Greece is very important since our dataset spanning from June 1994 to June 1999 is overlapping with a highly deflationary period as a result of the European Monetary Union convergence process. A rapidly growing emerging market covering the broader area of Balkans, is of great importance for the area. The simple OLS regression results are given below in Table 5 :

Table 5

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Greece			

Dependent variable is RS			
61 observations used for estimation from June 1994 to June 1999			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	-2.4805	3.7430	-.66269[.510]
INFL	-.94298	3.0856	-.30561[.761]

R-Squared	.0015805	R-Bar-Squared	-.015342
S.E. of Regression	26.5795	F-stat. F(1, 59)	.093395[.761]
Mean of Dependent Variable	-2.9567	S.D. of Dependent Variable	26.3779
Residual Sum of Squares	41681.6	Equation Log-likelihood	-285.6269
Akaike Info. Criterion	-287.6269	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	-289.7378
	DW-statistic		2.0362

$$R_i = -2.48(3.7430) - 0.94298(3.0856)p_i$$

We can see that in this case there is a very strong negative relationship between inflation and Stock Exchange returns. Nevertheless the standard errors are quite high and the t-ratios low and as such the results cannot be considered statistically significant. R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at 0.0015805 and -0.015342 respectively. Again no evidence of a relationship called the “Fisher effect”.

Hungary

Same story with Hungary too. We examine a dataset which starts as early as October 1995 and finishes quite recently in May 1999. Our results show illustrated in table 6 show no significant deviations from the previous results. In more detail β is no significantly different to zero, just as α is. We can see that R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at 0.0040700 and -0.09643 respectively

Table 6

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Hungary			

Dependent variable is RS			
44 observations used for estimation from October 1995 to May 1999			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.046403	.024389	1.9026[.064]
INFL	.016233	.039183	.41429[.681]

R-Squared	.0040700	R-Bar-Squared	-.019643
S.E. of Regression	.12823	F-stat. F(1, 42)	.17164[.681]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.040242	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.12699
Residual Sum of Squares	.69061	Equation Log-likelihood	28.9628
Akaike Info. Criterion	26.9628	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	25.1786
	DW-statistic	1.9422	

$$R_i = 0.046403(0.24389) + 0.016233(0.039183)p_i$$

Again we can see that we can't say anything about the Fisher effect since the evidence very clearly does not support it.

Indonesia

The first emerging country we examine from the South East Asia is Indonesia. No significantly different results too for Indonesia since the empirical evidence for this country does not support the so called Fisher effect. We examine a dataset starting in May 1996, ending in June 1999. Our results given below in table 7 show that α and β are again no different from zero. The R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand

at 0.017784 and -0.0095 respectively. The results are provided in the following table- table 7-. We can see again that the Fisher effect is not appearing in this case too.

Table 7

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Indonesia			

Dependent variable is RS			
38 observations used for estimation from May 1996 to June 1999			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.021600	.025442	.84901[.401]
INFL	-.0058714	.0072725	-.80735[.425]

R-Squared	.017784	R-Bar-Squared	-.0095000
S.E. of Regression	.13026	F-stat. F(1, 36)	.65181[.425]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.010162	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.12965
Residual Sum of Squares	.61086	Equation Log-likelihood	24.5593
Akaike Info. Criterion	22.5593	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	20.9217
DW-statistic		1.6853	

$$R_i = 0.021600(0.025442) - 0.0058714(0.0072725)p_i$$

Israel

Israel has been a rapidly growing emerging market representing the Middle East in our portfolio. The Israeli market is highly constituted from high-tech companies which specialize in microelectronics and other hi-tech areas such as military arms.

Again we see absolutely no evidence of the Fisher effect since the β coefficient is far from 1 rather closer to zero and just like in all the previous cases not statistically significant. The R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at almost 0 and -0.024387 respectively. A detailed table- table 8- is provided below. We should also point out that the dataset is from June 1995 to December 1998.

Table 8

```

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation
Israel
*****
Dependent variable is RS
43 observations used for estimation from June 1995 to December 1998
*****
Regressor          Coefficient          Standard Error          T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT              .012229              .013477                .90738[.370]
INF                 -.1773E-3           .014738                -.012028[.990]
*****
R-Squared           .3529E-5            R-Bar-Squared          -.024387
S.E. of Regression .054216            F-stat.   F( 1, 41)    .1447E-3[.990]
Mean of Dependent Variable .012101          S.D. of Dependent Variable .053566
Residual Sum of Squares .12051          Equation Log-likelihood 65.3455
Akaike Info. Criterion 63.3455        Schwarz Bayesian Criterion 61.5843
DW-statistic        1.8790
*****

```

$$R_i = 0.012229(0.013477) - 0.001773(0.014738)p_i$$

Mexico

Mexico is another very important emerging and rapidly growing market. Mexico is particularly important if we consider the exposure of the major US banks in the area.

Our sample for Mexico goes back as far as February 1992 with the last observation being the 15th of May 1999. Same story as before with the β coefficient being rather closer to zero than one. Extremely low values for the R^2 values. The R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at 0.0033095 and -0.0082799 respectively.

More details for the OLS results can be found in table 9 provided below

Table 9

```

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation
Mexico
*****
Dependent variable is RS
88 observations used for estimation from February 1992 to May 1999
*****
Regressor          Coefficient          Standard Error          T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT              .011988              .015815                .75803[.451]
INF                 .0043978            .0082297                .53438[.594]
*****
R-Squared           .0033095            R-Bar-Squared          -.0082799
S.E. of Regression .095078            F-stat.   F( 1, 86)    .28556[.594]
Mean of Dependent Variable .018476          S.D. of Dependent Variable .094687
Residual Sum of Squares .77743          Equation Log-likelihood 83.2139
Akaike Info. Criterion 81.2139        Schwarz Bayesian Criterion 78.7366
DW-statistic        2.0565
*****

```

$$R_i = .011988 (0.015815) + 0.0043978(0.082297)p_i$$

Philippines

Another south east Asian country. The results are provided in the table 10 below:

Table 10

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Philippines			

Dependent variable is RS			
29 observations used for estimation from February 1997 to June 1999			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	-.0067349	.033715	-.19976[.843]
INF	.0053348	.037414	.14259[.888]

R-Squared	.7524E-3	R-Bar-Squared	-.036257
S.E. of Regression	.12928	F-stat. F(1, 27)	.020331[.888]
Mean of Dependent Variable	-.0033595	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.12700
Residual Sum of Squares	.45125	Equation Log-likelihood	19.2147
Akaike Info. Criterion	17.2147	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	15.8474
DW-statistic	1.4679		

$$R_i = -0.0067349(0.033715) + 0.0053348(0.037414)p_i$$

We can see for once again that there is nothing particularly interesting with Philippines too since the results are in line with the previous one. . The β coefficient is again in this case statistically rather closer to zero than to one. Extremely low values for the R^2 values. The R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at 0.0007524 and -0.036257 respectively.

Poland

Poland is another very important country of the former Eastern European block since it was the first country back in the decade of eighties that started the political and economical reforms. In this case the OLS regression results are not different than in any of the countries we previously examined. The dataset examined goes

back to July of 1993 with the last observation being April 1994. The R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at 0.0041570 and -0.010488 respectively.

The results are provided in more detail below in table 11.

Table 11

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Poland			

Dependent variable is RS			
70 observations used for estimation from July 1993 to April 1999			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.035438	.019782	1.7914[.078]
INF	.0060773	.011407	.53278[.596]

R-Squared	.0041570	R-Bar-Squared	-.010488
S.E. of Regression	.16268	F-stat. F(1, 68)	.28385[.596]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.033499	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.16184
Residual Sum of Squares	1.7997	Equation Log-likelihood	28.8053
Akaike Info. Criterion	26.8053	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	24.5568
DW-statistic	1.9084		

$$R_i = 0.0035438(0.019782) + 0.0060773(0.011407)p_i$$

Portugal

The last emerging country we examine has many similarities with Greece. A rapidly and very strictly followed convergence program has been the case for the last years which successfully introduced the country into the Euro-zone. Nevertheless we examine again a broad dataset –from March 1993 to May 1999- which again shows absolutely no evidence for the Fisher effect support. The R^2 and R^2 adjusted for degrees of freedom stand at 0.0082206 and -0.0053654 respectively. Exactly the same story as previously with the coefficients being far away from supporting the so called Fisher effect. More information are provided in table below- Table 12-

Table 12

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Portugal			

Dependent variable is RS			
75 observations used for estimation from March 1993 to May 1999			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.014731	.0097747	1.5071[.136]
INF	.018489	.023769	.77787[.439]

R-Squared	.0082206	R-Bar-Squared	-.0053654
S.E. of Regression	.060689	F-stat. F(1, 73)	.60508[.439]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.020032	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.060527
Residual Sum of Squares	.26887	Equation Log-likelihood	104.7422
Akaike Info. Criterion	102.7422	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	100.4247
DW-statistic	1.6680		

$$R_i = 0.014731(0.0097747) + 0.018489(0.023769)p_i$$

2.3 Short term Interest Rates as Predictors of Inflation

Fama has shown and proven that Treasury bill returns or equivalent money market measures where the Treasury bill is not available can be used as a predictor of inflation. We have obtained 90 days treasury bill yields where available, while for the rest of the countries we have used the 90 days central bank discount rate or the implied swap rate from the interbank market. The assumption behind this is that the 90-Days interest rate observed at the middle of the month contains the market's assessment for the expected inflation for the next month. Formally the unexpected and unexpected components of inflation are observed from the following regression model:

$$\dot{p}_t = a + bI_{t-1} + e_t$$

Where I_{t-1} is the 90-day treasury bill yield quoted in the 15th of every month and π_t is the inflation rate observed during the month t . The regression results are provided in the next section of the analysis. Before we proceed to the next stage let us report that

Fama found for a set of highly industrialized countries that the b coefficient was not significantly statistically different from one. This can be interpreted as that changes in interest rates signal and correspond to changes in the inflation rate. Therefore if we find similar findings to Fama we will be able to examine the Fisher equation in terms of inflation but this time in terms of the expected and unexpected components of inflation. If we find in our research that expected inflation and interest rates move in a relationship close to 1 then we will proceed by examining the relationship between Stock returns, expected and unexpected inflation, while previously we did examine the relationship between stock returns and inflation.

Results

Below we outline the findings of the above regression for each country:

Argentina:

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	-.0016966	.14854	-.011422[.991]
TRATE(-1)	.010746	.015345	.70026[.486]

Brazil:

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	-.35235	.13423	-2.6250[.011]
TRATE(-1)	.023541	.0024342	9.6709[.000]

Chile

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	.77805	.17273	4.5045[.000]
TRATE(-1)	-.037354	.024187	-1.5444[.128]

Czech Republic

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	-.0014018	.0035545	-.39436[.695]
TRATE(-1)	.6479E-3	.2889E-3	2.2425[.029]

Greece

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	.47620	.47285	1.0071[.318]
TRATE(-1)	.0017378	.030598	.056794[.955]

Hungary

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	-.52600	.40144	-1.3103[.197]
TRATE(-1)	.0069206	.018619	.37169[.712]

Indonesia

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	.70427	1.0304	.68351[.499]
TRATE(-1)	.048386	.035621	1.3584[.183]

Israel

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	.014262	.0074110	1.9245[.061]
TRATE(-1)	-.5076E-3	.5276E-3	-.96216[.342]

Mexico

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	-.0046664	.0016690	-2.7960[.006]
TRATE(-1)	.7689E-3	.5955E-4	12.9121[.000]

Philippines

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	-.0040824	.0060035	-.68001[.502]
TRATE(-1)	.7584E-3	.4308E-3	1.7604[.090]

Poland

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	-.0068840	.0097674	-.70479[.483]
TRATE(-1)	.1435E-3	.3866E-3	.37115[.712]

Portugal

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	.0011702	.8562E-3	1.3667[.176]
TRATE(-1)	.2048E-3	.9564E-4	2.1410[.036]

We can see that in none of the cases above Fama's findings are confirmed, but we should always bear in mind that Fama was working on highly industrialized countries with highly developed capital markets. As a result of our findings splitting inflation into the expected and unexpected part would have been meaningless since the expected component of inflation is not captured by the interest rates in any of the cases whatsoever.

2.4 Conclusion

We have examined empirical evidence from a wide variety of countries utilizing the elementary OLS method of analysis. It is very clear from the results that none is in support of the Fisher effect, in fact we don't even find any statistically significant results. The case has been one of large standard errors and low R^2 values for all countries. From the all the above someone can conclude pretty much safely that at least within an emerging countries framework there doesn't exist such a thing called Fisher effect. Possible explanations include the fact that these countries probably suffer from their underdeveloped capital markets, so we might be facing a case where the market does not respond fast or not even at all to news in relation to inflation. The above explanation has been forward by Solnik who examined the Fisher effect in relation to a dataset taken from a very developed set of countries and he justified this action by outlining the above explanation. At this point someone might be in fact very critical by outlining the assumptions of Rational Expectations, and Market efficiency which are assumed to hold at any given moment in time. Another possible explanation for the results is the fact that there does not exist a relatively large dataset for developing countries and as such our results lack any statistical significance.

In some cases we observed a negative relationship between inflation and stock returns. Although not statistically significant in our case the phenomenon is statistically significant in many other pieces of evidence. The theory of monetary economics is outlining a possible explanation that could capture this negative relationship. In the next section we will examine the so called Fama Proxy Hypothesis which has been giving an alternative, a more refined explanation of the Fisher effect which is able in some cases to explain the contradicting empirical evidence.

Chapter III

3.1 The Fama Proxy Hypothesis

Fama Proxy hypothesis was introduced in 1981 and it states the observed inverse relationship between real stock returns and inflation is spurious. Inflation is simply a proxy variable for relating stock returns with inflation. Under the above hypothesis the negative relationship between stock returns found in most empirical evidence is the combined effect of two underlying relationships.

1. That between stock returns and expected economic activity.
2. That between expected economic activity and inflation.

The explanation of a positive relationship between stock returns and inflation is the result of expectations of higher dividends in the future while a negative relationship is implied from money demand effects arising from a rational expectations version of the quantity theory. The Fama Proxy Hypothesis has been a very important one since it is able to provide us with an economic theory explanation for the phenomenon that is observed almost universally, in most of the research on the issue. We can conclude from the above that in regressions of stock returns on inflation a statistically significant negative coefficient on the variable that captures the inflation term reflects these two underlying relationships. Most of the empirical evidence today does not incorporate any long-run relationship that might exist between stock returns and inflation. We should also point out that the Real Balance effect outlined by monetarist economists as a possible explanation for this negative relationship between stock returns and inflation can only hold in the short run. These remarks bring us to next section of our analysis which is related to an alternative approach to testing the Fama Proxy Hypothesis.

3.2 A Cointegration approach to the Fisher Effect

We have already established by utilising the simple OLS analysis in previous stage of our analysis that the Fisher effect is not supported in our dataset. We have also outlined a number of reasons why this might be the case. The question arising at this point is ,’ Is there any relationship between emerging countries stock indices and inflation. At this stage we will attempt to utilise a more advanced econometric technique than the ones we have already make use of. In fact Long and Short run Fisher effects have been considered very extensively with new tests. There has been noticed a support for the long-run “version” of the Fisher effect. In a series of recent papers it is argued extensively that the Fisher effect can only be considered in the long-run rather than the short-run something which of course comes in contrast with what has already been established in the introduction of this essay. In any case we must report that Atkins(1989), Bonham(1991), Mishkin(1992), Owen(1993) and finally Wallace and Warner (1993) have all found by utilising recent cointegration techniques some empirical evidence for long run support of the Fisher effect. Let us examine now what is the reasoning behind the utilisation of cointegration for the analysis of the long-run Fisher effect.

If stocks provide a hedge against inflation, then stock prices and the Consumer Price Index(CPI) should move together over time or in other words they should be Cointegrated.. When variables are cointegrated their long-term trends adjust to an equilibrium constraint. Deviations of these series from their equilibrium values are transitory in nature and are appropriately modelled in the structure of Error Correction Models (ECM). In other words cointegration techniques since they allow us to examine the presence of a long run relationship between stock indices in our case and

inflation offer a very nice way to explore whether there exists such a thing as the Fisher effect.

3.3 Empirical Analysis

Let us now examine the definition of cointegration within a theoretical framework:

If $x_t \sim I(1)$, but there exists an m -vector \mathbf{a} such that $\mathbf{a}'x_t \sim I(0)$, the variables are said to be cointegrated \mathbf{a} is called a cointegrating vector.

In other words, cointegrated variables are trended processes sharing a common trend. Any indication of a long-run comovement among stationary $I(1)$ variables is definitely cointegration.

For cointegration to exist, the variables under consideration must all be difference-stationary. They must be integrated of order 1 or in other words $I(1)$ as has already been established. This is a very crucial point for the analysis to be valid

We will be testing the variables- whether they are $I(0)$ or $I(1)$ -, in our case the Stock exchange index for each country and also the Consumer Price Index. Before we proceed to this stage we must say that we will be using the log-linear form of the variables. In other words we will be examining the logarithms of CPI and the Stock index for each different country. We will pursue the above analysis by utilising the Augmented Dickey Fuller test, or the ADF test. We will pursue the ADF tests by denoting a lag of 12, something that is reasonable if we consider that we are dealing with monthly data. We should mention here that this is a residual-based test for stationarity. Microfit provides us with two different tables for the determination of the stationarity of the variables . The first includes intercept but not a trend and the second one includes both intercept and a time trend. The decision upon which table

should be used is left entirely to us after we plot the variables. In the presence of a clear time trend we have to use the second table which allows for it. There are two the criteria we will be utilising in order to determine the degree of stationarity. Firstly we will be using the Schwartz- Bayesian criterion (SBC) and secondly the Akaike Information (AIC) criterion.

If we find clear evidence of stationarity for the variables- in other words if they are I(1)- then we can proceed with a VAR analysis. If otherwise we must proceed with an ARDL approach to Error Correction Model (ECM) which can be utilised no matter if the variables are I(0) or I(1). In our case although we will examine the variables for stationarity we will utilise the ARDL analysis as this has been described by Pesaran and Pesaran in their book 'Working with Microfit 4.0'.

3.4 Unit Root Tests

The unit root tests for each country include tests for both the logarithm of the Stock Index and the logarithm of the Consumer price index. As noted previously we will be utilising the maximum order of lag- that is 12- since we are dealing with monthly data. We will be considering whether we should use the intercept only or the intercept/trend table according to the plot of each variable. The decision upon the stationarity will be based in accordance to the Schwartz- Bayesian criterion. The null hypothesis is non-trend stationarity while the alternative is trend stationarity.

H₀-Null Hypothesis-: Non Trend Stationarity- I(0).

H₁: Trend Stationarity-I(1).

Argentina

The plots for the Logarithm of the stock index and CPI are provided below (Figures 1 and 2):

Figure 1: Plot of Stock Index for Argentina

Figure 2: Plot of CPI for Argentina

From the two plots we can see that while for the CPI there exists a very clear trend we cannot say the same for the Stock index. Consequently for the Stock index we choose

the ADF test with no trend while for the CPI we choose the test that includes an intercept and a trend. The tables of the ADF tests are provided below-tables 1,2-

Table 1: ADF test for Argentinean Stock Index

```

Unit root tests for variable LMerval
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept but not a trend
*****
58 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1994M9 to 1999M6
*****

```

DF	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
	-1.9865*	42.0494	40.0494	37.9890*	39.2468
ADF(1)	-2.0157	42.1457	39.1457	36.0551	37.9419
ADF(2)	-1.8340	42.2174	38.2174	34.0965	36.6122
ADF(3)	-1.5517	42.6179	37.6179	32.4668	35.6114
ADF(4)	-1.6625	42.8751	36.8751	30.6938	34.4673
ADF(5)	-1.7705	43.1243	36.1243	28.9128	33.3153
ADF(6)	-1.6924	43.1243	35.1243	26.8825	31.9140
ADF(7)	-1.9334	43.9687	34.9687	25.6967	31.3571
ADF(8)	-1.9846	44.1251	34.1251	23.8229	30.1122
ADF(9)	-1.9566	44.1843	33.1843	21.8519	28.7701
ADF(10)	-2.5639	46.4353	34.4353	22.0727	29.6198
ADF(11)	-2.1833	46.6334	33.6334	20.2406	28.4166
ADF(12)	-2.0898	46.6415	32.6415	18.2184	27.0234

```

*****
95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = *-2.9118
LL = Maximized log-likelihood      AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion    HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

```

Table 2: ADF test for Argentinean CPI

```

Unit root tests for variable CPI
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend
*****
58 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1994M9 to 1999M6
*****

```

DF	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
	-2.9228*	-482.6666	-485.6666	-488.7573*	-486.8705
ADF(1)	-3.0370	-482.2800	-486.2800	-490.4009	-487.8851
ADF(2)	-2.9033	-481.2086	-486.2086	-491.3598	-488.2151
ADF(3)	-2.9621	-479.8546	-485.8546	-492.0360	-488.2624
ADF(4)	-3.0336	-479.2517	-486.2517	-493.4632	-489.0607
ADF(5)	-2.9826	-479.2324	-487.2324	-495.4742	-490.4427
ADF(6)	-3.1447	-476.1715	-485.1715	-494.4435	-488.7831
ADF(7)	-3.0013	-476.1381	-486.1381	-496.4403	-490.1510
ADF(8)	-2.9078	-476.1318	-487.1318	-498.4643	-491.5460
ADF(9)	-2.7577	-475.9929	-487.9929	-500.3555	-492.8084
ADF(10)	-2.5218	-474.8000	-487.8000	-501.1929	-493.0168
ADF(11)	-2.4983	-474.7769	-488.7769	-503.2000	-494.3949
ADF(12)	-2.3002	-473.5209	-488.5209	-503.9743	-494.5403

```

*****
95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.4875*
LL = Maximized log-likelihood      AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion    HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

```

Since in both cases the $|ADF - statistic| > |test - statistic|$ we cannot reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity.

Brazil

We begin by plotting the logarithms of the Stock index and the CPI in order to determine whether we should include a trend or not. Graphs 3 and 4 outline the case

Graph 3: Plot of the Brazilian Stock Index

Graph 4: Plot of the Brazilian CPI

From the graphs above it is very clearly evident that we ought in this case use the tables that include both an intercept and a trend. Although there is absolutely no doubt about the CPI someone might question the choice of using the trend\intercept table for the case of the Stock index. We will stick with the choice of trend\intercept since it is very clear that there exists a long term trend in the stock index which is not out weighted by some short term swings of the index. In the following tables- tables 3 and 4- we provide the ADF tests-unit root tests- for the LBOVESPA and LCPI variables

Table 3: Unit Root test for The Brazilian Stock Index

Unit root tests for variable LBOVESPA					
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend					

44 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.					
Sample period from 1995M11 to 1999M6					

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-2.0631*	30.0755	27.0755	24.3992*	26.0830
ADF(1)	-1.8003	30.2974	26.2974	22.7290	24.9741
ADF(2)	-1.8319	30.3993	25.3993	20.9389	23.7452
ADF(3)	-1.8051	30.4183	24.4183	19.0657	22.4333
ADF(4)	-2.2821	32.8052	25.8052	19.5606	23.4894
ADF(5)	-2.0434	32.8490	24.8490	17.7122	22.2023
ADF(6)	-1.4300	33.7974	24.7974	16.7686	21.8200
ADF(7)	-1.2649	33.9147	23.9147	14.9938	20.6064
ADF(8)	-.88238	34.6588	23.6588	13.8458	20.0197
ADF(9)	-1.1264	35.1063	23.1063	12.4012	19.1363
ADF(10)	-2.4989	39.9024	26.9024	15.3051	22.6016
ADF(11)	-2.1611	39.9278	25.9278	13.4385	21.2961
ADF(12)	-2.5640	41.3394	26.3394	12.9580	21.3769

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.5136*					
LL = Maximized log-likelihood		AIC = Akaike Information Criterion			
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion		HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion			

Table 4: Unit Root test for Brazilian CPI

Unit root tests for variable LCPI					
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend					

43 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.					
Sample period from 1995M11 to 1999M5					

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-3.9590	177.9903	174.9903	172.3485	174.0160
ADF(1)	-3.1721	188.7885	184.7885	181.2661	183.4896
ADF(2)	-3.0949*	191.6682	186.6682	182.2652*	185.0445
ADF(3)	-3.0904	191.9722	185.9722	180.6886	184.0238
ADF(4)	-3.4497	193.2672	186.2672	180.1030	183.9941
ADF(5)	-3.0758	193.3299	185.3299	178.2851	182.7320
ADF(6)	-3.4700	194.8304	185.8304	177.9050	182.9077
ADF(7)	-4.2679	197.8495	187.8495	179.0435	184.6021
ADF(8)	-5.0837	201.1647	190.1647	180.4781	186.5926
ADF(9)	-4.3226	201.3364	189.3364	178.7692	185.4396
ADF(10)	-4.7728	203.9594	190.9594	179.5116	186.7378
ADF(11)	-4.2751	204.7718	190.7718	178.4434	186.2254
ADF(12)	-3.6721	205.6365	190.6365	177.4275	185.7654

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.5162*					
LL = Maximized log-likelihood		AIC = Akaike Information Criterion			
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion		HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion			

Since in both cases the $|ADF - statistic| > |test - statistic|$ we cannot reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity.

Chile

The graphs below, graphs 5 and 6 outline the case for Chile. As we can see below for the Chilean stock index we should consult the table where the only factor considered is the intercept since there is very clearly no evidence of a time trend. On the other hand the LCPI variable does very clearly contain a time trend.

Table 5: Chilean Stock Index Graph

Graph 6: Plot of the Chilean CPI

The next two tables, tables 5 and 6 provide the unit root tests for LIGPA and LCPI for Chile. For LIGPA intercept but not trend will be used while for LCPI intercept and trend is the case.

Table 5: Unit Root test for LIGPA

Unit root tests for variable LIGPA					
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept but not a trend					

52 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.					
Sample period from 1995M2 to 1999M5					

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.2508*	73.4309	71.4309	69.4797*	70.6829
ADF(1)	-1.2964	73.5250	70.5250	67.5982	69.4029
ADF(2)	-1.2155	73.5484	69.5484	65.6459	68.0523
ADF(3)	-1.0389	73.7554	68.7554	63.8773	66.8852
ADF(4)	-1.6037	76.1249	70.1249	64.2712	67.8808
ADF(5)	-1.2875	76.3463	69.3463	62.5170	66.7281
ADF(6)	-.99396	76.9591	68.9591	61.1541	65.9668
ADF(7)	-1.7942	80.0450	71.0450	62.2644	67.6788
ADF(8)	-1.8386	80.2522	70.2522	60.4959	66.5119
ADF(9)	-2.3405	81.5953	70.5953	59.8634	66.4809
ADF(10)	-2.1068	81.7558	69.7558	58.0484	65.2675
ADF(11)	-1.8975	81.8102	68.8102	56.1271	63.9478
ADF(12)	-2.1056	82.5424	68.5424	54.8837	63.3060

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -2.9179*					
LL = Maximized log-likelihood AIC = Akaike Information Criterion					
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion					

Table 6: Unit Root test for LCPI

Unit root tests for variable LCPI					
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend					

52 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.					
Sample period from 1995M2 to 1999M5					

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.1090*	228.7190	225.7190	222.7921*	224.5969
ADF(1)	-1.2335	229.1264	225.1264	221.2239	223.6303
ADF(2)	-1.1850	229.1264	224.1264	219.2483	222.2563
ADF(3)	-.90539	229.4237	223.4237	217.5699	221.1795
ADF(4)	-.34296	232.0636	225.0636	218.2342	222.4454
ADF(5)	-.13069	233.1747	225.1747	217.3698	222.1825
ADF(6)	-.11322	233.1814	224.1814	215.4008	220.8151
ADF(7)	.079150	234.2553	224.2553	214.4991	220.5150
ADF(8)	.27266	234.7380	223.7380	213.0061	219.6237
ADF(9)	.32677	234.8662	222.8662	211.1587	218.3778
ADF(10)	.65408	237.4081	224.4081	211.7250	219.5457
ADF(11)	.72227	237.6949	223.6949	210.0362	218.4585
ADF(12)	.57847	237.9374	222.9374	208.3031	217.3269

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.4969*					
LL = Maximized log-likelihood AIC = Akaike Information Criterion					
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion					

Again we cannot reject the null hypothesis of stationarity in both cases since the

$$|ADF - statistic| > |test - statistic|.$$

Czech Republic

There is a similar story for Czech Republic too. We do not see any evidence from the following graph-graph 7- that we should include a trend into the analysis of the Stock index. The time series “looks” in a sense to be mean reverting in the long run. While this is the case with the Stock index, exactly the opposite, just as it is expected from the type of the time series- is the case for the CPI-graph 8-, that it keeps increasing with a very clear and visually constant rate. Summarizing we will use an intercept but not trend for the Stock index while we will utilize an intercept and a trend for the Consumer’s Price index.

Graph 7:Plot of Czech Stock Index

Graph 8:Plot of Czech Consumer Price Index

Next, we provide the tables with the unit root tests for LPX50 and LCPI-tables 7 and 8-.

Table 7: Unit Root Test for Czech Stock Index

Unit root tests for variable LPX50
 The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept but not a trend

 50 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
 Sample period from 1995M5 to 1999M6

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.9948*	61.1908	59.1908	57.2788*	58.4627
ADF(1)	-2.2136	61.8094	58.8094	55.9414	57.7173
ADF(2)	-1.9424	61.9354	57.9354	54.1113	56.4791
ADF(3)	-1.8151	61.9411	56.9411	52.1610	55.1208
ADF(4)	-1.7196	61.9422	55.9422	50.2061	53.7578
ADF(5)	-1.7320	62.0105	55.0105	48.3184	52.4621
ADF(6)	-2.0940	63.3254	55.3254	47.6773	52.4130
ADF(7)	-2.4343	64.4832	55.4832	46.8791	52.2067
ADF(8)	-2.4973	64.7533	54.7533	45.1932	51.1127
ADF(9)	-2.1027	64.8806	53.8806	43.3645	49.8760
ADF(10)	-2.3449	65.6215	53.6215	42.1494	49.2529
ADF(11)	-2.1970	65.6216	52.6216	40.1934	47.8889
ADF(12)	-2.1072	65.6229	51.6229	38.2387	46.5261

 95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = **-2.9202***
 LL = Maximized log-likelihood AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
 SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

Table 8: Unit Root Test for Czech Consumer's Price Index

Unit root tests for variable LCPI
 The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend

 50 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
 Sample period from 1995M5 to 1999M6

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-.56338	171.7236	168.7236	165.8556	167.6315
ADF(1)	-.81071	172.0337	168.0337	164.2097	166.5775
ADF(2)	-.59770	172.1049	167.1049	162.3249	165.2846
ADF(3)	-.60361	172.1187	166.1187	160.3827	163.9344
ADF(4)	-.28230	172.3934	165.3934	158.7013	162.8450
ADF(5)	-.27417	172.3944	164.3944	156.7463	161.4820
ADF(6)	-2.7792*	187.6752	178.6752	170.0711*	175.3987
ADF(7)	-2.9877	188.5339	178.5339	168.9738	174.8933
ADF(8)	-2.7567	188.7060	177.7060	167.1899	173.7014
ADF(9)	-3.0391	189.7492	177.7492	166.2771	173.3805
ADF(10)	-2.4687	189.7575	176.7575	164.3294	172.0248
ADF(11)	-1.9886	189.8913	175.8913	162.5072	170.7946
ADF(12)	-2.6620	192.1814	177.1814	162.8412	171.7205

 95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = **-3.5005***
 LL = Maximized log-likelihood AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
 SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

Another case where we cannot reject the hypothesis that both variables are I(0) since

the $|ADF - statistic| > |test - statistic|$.

Greece

The case of Greece outlined below in graphs 9 and 10, is a case where we should be using both the intercept and trend into the analysis. The graphs provide the proof for that.

Graph 9:Plot of the Greek Stock Index

Graph 10 :Plot of the Greek Consumer's Price Index

In the next stage we provide the Unit root tests for the Greek Stock Index and Consumer's Price index including in both cases an intercept and a time trend. Tables 9 and 10. Again we can see that there is no evidence why we should accept the alternative hypothesis since in both cases for the Athens General index and the consumer's price index the Absolute value of the Augmented Dickey Fuller test is greater than the correspondent statistic- $|ADF - statistic| > |test - statistic|$.

Table 9: Unit root test for the Greek Stock Index

Unit root tests for variable LATHENSGE
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend

50 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1995M5 to 1999M6

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-2.0466*	47.1656	44.1656	41.2976*	43.0735
ADF(1)	-2.3082	47.8578	43.8578	40.0338	42.4016
ADF(2)	-2.3196	47.9950	42.9950	38.2150	41.1748
ADF(3)	-2.1300	47.9961	41.9961	36.2600	39.8117
ADF(4)	-2.1086	48.0736	41.0736	34.3815	38.5252
ADF(5)	-1.1732	52.1974	44.1974	36.5493	41.2849
ADF(6)	-.99699	52.4175	43.4175	34.8134	40.1410
ADF(7)	-1.0634	52.5881	42.5881	33.0279	38.9475
ADF(8)	-1.0183	52.6061	41.6061	31.0899	37.6015
ADF(9)	-.79867	55.5051	43.5051	32.0330	39.1364
ADF(10)	-.77204	55.5221	42.5221	30.0940	37.7894
ADF(11)	-.36540	58.1847	44.1847	30.8005	39.0879
ADF(12)	-.35869	58.1891	43.1891	28.8489	37.7283

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = **-3.5005***
LL = Maximized log-likelihood AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

Table 10: Unit root test for the Greek Consumer's Price Index

Unit root tests for variable LCPI
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend

50 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1995M5 to 1999M6

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-2.9580	158.6795	155.6795	152.8115	154.5874
ADF(1)	-3.4121	160.1019	156.1019	152.2779	154.6457
ADF(2)	-2.3303	163.4468	158.4468	153.6667	156.6265
ADF(3)	-2.3992	163.6726	157.6726	151.9365	155.4882
ADF(4)	-.69225	184.4392	177.4392	170.7471	174.8908
ADF(5)	-.83041	185.0815	177.0815	169.4334	174.1691
ADF(6)	-1.1255	186.7194	177.7194	169.1153	174.4429
ADF(7)	-.97892	186.8651	176.8651	167.3050	173.2246
ADF(8)	-.84997	187.0475	176.0475	165.5314	172.0429
ADF(9)	-.69869	188.2980	176.2980	164.8258	171.9293
ADF(10)	-.15151	206.7031	193.7031	181.2750	188.9704
ADF(11)	.055587	209.1164	195.1164	181.7322	190.0196
ADF(12)	.19145*	225.3089	210.3089	195.9687*	204.8481

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = **-3.5005***
LL = Maximized log-likelihood AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

Hungary

Graphs 11 and 12 provide the information we need in the case of Hungary for a decision on the subject whether we should use or not an intercept only or a combination of an intercept and a trend for the Unit root tests. It is very clearly indicated by the graph-graph 11- that there is a downward sloping trend in this case for the Hungarian Stock index. As a result we will be including the trend in the unit root test for the Hungarian Stock Index. For the case of the Consumers Price index once again as expected for the kind of the variable we will be including a trend to the unit root test since it is very evident that there is a trend as indicated by graph 12.

Graph 11: Plot of the Hungarian Stock Index

Graph 12: Plot of the Hungarian Consumer's Price Index

In the next stage of the analysis and in particular in tables 11 and 12 we provide the Unit root tests for the Hungarian Stock Index and Consumer's Price Index including an intercept and a trend.

Table 11: Unit root test for the Hungarian Stock Index

```

Unit root tests for variable LBUX
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend
*****
32 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1996M10 to 1999M5
*****

```

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-2.1113*	22.7243	19.7243	17.5257*	18.9955
ADF(1)	-2.1444	22.8700	18.8700	15.9385	17.8983
ADF(2)	-1.8220	24.6320	19.6320	15.9677	18.4174
ADF(3)	-1.8186	24.6936	18.6936	14.2964	17.2361
ADF(4)	-1.6562	25.0788	18.0788	12.9487	16.3783
ADF(5)	-1.6617	25.1626	17.1626	11.2997	15.2192
ADF(6)	-1.6042	25.1626	16.1626	9.5668	13.9763
ADF(7)	-1.6880	25.4394	15.4394	8.1108	13.0102
ADF(8)	-1.1052	25.9336	14.9336	6.8720	12.2614
ADF(9)	-.56912	26.1963	14.1963	5.4019	11.2812
ADF(10)	-.30902	26.5710	13.5710	4.0437	10.4129
ADF(11)	-.46888	26.7681	12.7681	2.5079	9.3671
ADF(12)	-.70018	27.0575	12.0575	1.0645	8.4136

```

*****
95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.5562*
LL = Maximized log-likelihood      AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion    HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

```

Table 12: Unit root test for the Hungarian Consumer's Price Index

```

Unit root tests for variable LCPI
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend
*****
32 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1996M10 to 1999M5
*****

```

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.1178*	128.9069	125.9069	123.7083*	125.1781
ADF(1)	-1.1086	128.9242	124.9242	121.9927	123.9525
ADF(2)	-1.3333	129.4608	124.4608	120.7965	123.2462
ADF(3)	-2.1829	132.5184	126.5184	122.1212	125.0609
ADF(4)	-2.1459	132.7176	125.7176	120.5875	124.0171
ADF(5)	-2.4616	133.6166	125.6166	119.7537	123.6732
ADF(6)	-3.4764	137.1043	128.1043	121.5085	125.9179
ADF(7)	-3.6406	137.8978	127.8978	120.5691	125.4685
ADF(8)	-4.1860	140.1071	129.1071	121.0455	126.4349
ADF(9)	-3.9278	140.7017	128.7017	119.9072	125.7866
ADF(10)	-4.6294	143.7096	130.7096	121.1823	127.5516
ADF(11)	-5.4087	147.5949	133.5949	123.3347	130.1939
ADF(12)	-3.2845	147.9726	132.9726	121.9796	129.3287

```

*****
95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.5562*
LL = Maximized log-likelihood      AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion    HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

```

From the above unit root tests again it is not evident that we can reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity. The data do not seem to support existence of any unit roots whatsoever. Again as previously the Absolute value of the Augmented Dickey

Fuller tests is greater than the correspondent statistic for both variables $|ADF - statistic| > |test - statistic|$.

Indonesia

Graphs 13 and 14 provided below give us the necessary tools to answer whether we need or not an intercept and a trend for the Augmented Dickey Fuller tests for the case of the Indonesian Stock Index and Consumer Price Index. In this case and as it is shown by graph 13 which is the graph of the Indonesian Stock index it is not clear whether we should or should not use a trend in addition to the intercept. In the long run the pattern may exhibit some trend but there are many swings especially after the South- East Asian crises that does not allow us to consider a trend. For the case of the Indonesian Consumer's Price index illustrated in graph 14 thing are much easier to interpret since just like in any other case there is a very clear trend captured in the graph. Summarizing we will pursue the ADF tests by utilising an intercept but no trend in the case of the stock index and an intercept with a trend in the case of the Consumer's price index.

Graph 13: Plot of the Indonesian Stock Index

Graph 14: Plot of the Indonesian Consumer's Price index

The next stage involves the Augmented Dickey Fuller tests which are both provided below in tables 13 and 14 respectively.

Table 13: Unit root test of the Indonesian stock Index

```

Unit root tests for variable LJAKARTA
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept but not a trend
*****
26 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1997M5 to 1999M6
*****

```

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.6499*	12.6346	10.6346	9.3765*	10.2723
ADF(1)	-1.9397	13.4335	10.4335	8.5464	9.8901
ADF(2)	-1.6276	13.8049	9.8049	7.2887	9.0803
ADF(3)	-1.5666	13.8053	8.8053	5.6601	7.8996
ADF(4)	-1.6425	14.1247	8.1247	4.3504	7.0379
ADF(5)	-1.6516	14.2242	7.2242	2.8209	5.9562
ADF(6)	-1.9610	15.3793	7.3793	2.3469	5.9302
ADF(7)	-1.5224	15.9473	6.9473	1.2859	5.3170
ADF(8)	-1.5214	16.0461	6.0461	-.24443	4.2346
ADF(9)	-1.3657	16.0478	5.0478	-1.8718	3.0552
ADF(10)	-1.4544	16.3585	4.3585	-3.1901	2.1848
ADF(11)	-1.2169	16.5069	3.5069	-4.6707	1.1521
ADF(12)	-1.3232	16.9761	2.9761	-5.8306	.44005

```

*****
*
95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -2.9798*
LL = Maximized log-likelihood      AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion    HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

```

Again in this case no evidence of stationarity for the LJAKARTA variable since the Unit root test proves that we cannot reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity in any case.

Table 14: Unit root test of the Indonesian Consumer's Price Index

Unit root tests for variable LCPI					
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend					

26 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.					
Sample period from 1997M5 to 1999M6					

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-.38533	53.6944	50.6944	48.8073	50.1510
ADF(1)	-1.8248*	64.2052	60.2052	57.6890*	59.4806
ADF(2)	-1.5331	64.2757	59.2757	56.1305	58.3700
ADF(3)	-1.8613	65.3516	59.3516	55.5773	58.2648
ADF(4)	-2.2727	66.6671	59.6671	55.2637	58.3991
ADF(5)	-3.2456	70.2669	62.2669	57.2345	60.8178
ADF(6)	-3.5483	71.7162	62.7162	57.0548	61.0860
ADF(7)	-3.2388	71.9927	61.9927	55.7022	60.1813
ADF(8)	-2.7224	72.0998	61.0998	54.1803	59.1072
ADF(9)	-2.5960	72.1041	60.1041	52.5556	57.9304
ADF(10)	-2.3844	72.2584	59.2584	51.0808	56.9036
ADF(11)	-2.2837	72.2596	58.2596	49.4530	55.7236
ADF(12)	-2.2418	72.4600	57.4600	48.0242	54.7428

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.5943*					
LL = Maximized log-likelihood		AIC = Akaike Information Criterion			
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion		HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion			

We cannot reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity again it is pretty evident that neither the LCPI or the LJAKARTA variables can be considered as I(0) variables since we can see that the Absolute value of the Augmented Dickey Fuller tests is greater than the correspondent statistic for both variables $|ADF - statistic| > |test - statistic|$.

Israel

Graphs 15 and 16 provide us with the answer to the question if we should include in addition to an intercept a trend to the Unit root tests for the Israeli stock and consumer price indices. For both cases the inclusion of an intercept and a trend is judged as necessary from the evidence provided from the graphs. Both variables have a very clear trend component.

Graph 15: Plot of Israeli Stock Index

Graph 16: Plot of Israeli Consumer Price Index

The next two tables 15 and 16 provide the unit root tests for the Israeli Stock and consumer price indices.

Table 15: Unit Root Test for the Israeli stock index

```

Unit root tests for variable LTELAV
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend
*****
31 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1996M6 to 1998M12
*****

```

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.2269	47.0467	44.0467	41.8957	43.3456
ADF(1)	-1.4602	47.5422	43.5422	40.6742	42.6073
ADF(2)	-1.9943	48.9026	43.9026	40.3176	42.7340
ADF(3)	-1.9378	49.0033	43.0033	38.7013	41.6009
ADF(4)	-2.1866	49.6664	42.6664	37.6475	41.0304
ADF(5)	-2.4450	50.4453	42.4453	36.7094	40.5755
ADF(6)	-1.9411	50.5507	41.5507	35.0978	39.4472
ADF(7)	-1.6764	50.5957	40.5957	33.4258	38.2585
ADF(8)	-2.3634	53.5748	42.5748	34.6879	40.0038
ADF(9)	-2.4921	54.1741	42.1741	33.5702	39.3694
ADF(10)	-2.0728	54.1748	41.1748	31.8539	38.1364
ADF(11)	-2.5785	55.9852	41.9852	31.9473	38.7131
ADF(12)	-2.2766	56.0587	41.0587	30.3038	37.5528

```

*****
95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.5615
LL = Maximized log-likelihood      AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion    HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

```

Table 16: Unit Root Test for the Israeli Consumer's Price Index

Unit root tests for variable LCPI					
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend					

31 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.					
Sample period from 1996M6 to 1998M12					

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.1298	116.0462	113.0462	110.8952	112.3451
ADF(1)	-2.1785*	120.1805	116.1805	113.3125*	115.2456
ADF(2)	-1.7184	120.4934	115.4934	111.9084	114.3247
ADF(3)	-1.8366	120.9211	114.9211	110.6192	113.5188
ADF(4)	-1.8394	121.0038	114.0038	108.9849	112.3678
ADF(5)	-1.7255	121.0514	113.0514	107.3155	111.1816
ADF(6)	-1.8822	121.9912	112.9912	106.5382	110.8877
ADF(7)	-1.5510	122.6757	112.6757	105.5058	110.3385
ADF(8)	-1.5961	122.8880	111.8880	104.0011	109.3171
ADF(9)	-1.2873	123.2816	111.2816	102.6777	108.4770
ADF(10)	-1.2181	123.2834	110.2834	100.9625	107.2451
ADF(11)	-.73774	125.1232	111.1232	101.0853	107.8511
ADF(12)	-.75839	125.1825	110.1825	99.4276	106.6767

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.5615*					
LL = Maximized log-likelihood AIC = Akaike Information Criterion					
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion					

We can see that for both variables we cannot reject the null hypothesis of non cointegration since the Absolute value of the Augmented Dickey Fuller tests is greater than the correspondent statistic for both variables $|ADF - statistic| > |test - statistic|$ -. We can proceed and say with certainty that the variables are not I(1).

Mexico

The next country is Mexico. Graphs 17 and 18 provide the tool to decide whether we should include a trend for the Mexican stock and consumer price indices. The answer for both variables is that we should definitely pursue the unit root tests using a trend too since the plots reveal that there is a trend component in both variables.

Graph 17: Plot of Mexican Stock Index

Graph 18: Plot of Mexican Consumer Price Index

We continue by pursuing the unit root tests for both variables by including both an intercept and a trend. The unit root tests are provided in tables 17 and 18 for the stock index and the consumer's price index respectively.

Table 17: Unit root test for Mexican Stock Index

Unit root tests for variable LIPC

The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend

 76 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
 Sample period from 1993M2 to 1999M5

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-2.6795*	73.7495	70.7495	67.2534*	69.3523
ADF(1)	-2.6018	73.7735	69.7735	65.1120	67.9105
ADF(2)	-2.5518	73.8139	68.8139	62.9871	66.4852
ADF(3)	-2.8583	74.8357	68.8357	61.8435	66.0413
ADF(4)	-2.7888	74.8851	67.8851	59.7276	64.6250
ADF(5)	-3.0662	75.8005	67.8005	58.4776	64.0746
ADF(6)	-2.5511	76.1869	67.1869	56.6986	62.9952
ADF(7)	-2.7995	76.9866	66.9866	55.3329	62.3292
ADF(8)	-2.9239	77.4312	66.4312	53.6122	61.3081
ADF(9)	-3.0241	77.9006	65.9006	51.9162	60.3118
ADF(10)	-3.7909	81.2629	68.2629	53.1131	62.2083
ADF(11)	-3.1550	81.4913	67.4913	51.1761	60.9710
ADF(12)	-3.3475	82.2494	67.2494	49.7689	60.2634

 95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = **-3.4688***
 LL = Maximized log-likelihood AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
 SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

Table 18: Unit root test for Mexican Consumer Price Index

Unit root tests for variable LCPI					
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend					

76 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.					
Sample period from 1993M2 to 1999M5					

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.4093	225.9234	222.9234	219.4273	221.5262
ADF(1)	-2.6696*	270.8228	266.8228	262.1613*	264.9599
ADF(2)	-2.2637	271.6583	266.6583	260.8315	264.3296
ADF(3)	-2.1889	271.6659	265.6659	258.6737	262.8715
ADF(4)	-1.9421	272.6411	265.6411	257.4835	262.3809
ADF(5)	-2.3303	275.6672	267.6672	258.3443	263.9413
ADF(6)	-2.4037	275.9095	266.9095	256.4212	262.7178
ADF(7)	-2.7885	278.1545	268.1545	256.5009	263.4972
ADF(8)	-2.7815	278.2375	267.2375	254.4185	262.1144
ADF(9)	-2.8757	278.5864	266.5864	252.6020	260.9975
ADF(10)	-2.6208	278.8451	265.8451	250.6953	259.7905
ADF(11)	-3.2156	282.8991	268.8991	252.5840	262.3788
ADF(12)	-3.3101	283.3275	268.3275	250.8470	261.3414

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.4688*					
LL = Maximized log-likelihood AIC = Akaike Information Criterion					
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion					

For once again we cannot reject the null hypothesis of non stationarity since in neither of cases the absolute value of the Augmented Dickey Fuller tests is greater than the correspondent statistic for both variables $|ADF - statistic| > |test - statistic|$ -. We can proceed and say with certainty that the variables are not I(1).

Philippines

Graphs 19 and 20 determine whether we should or we shouldn't use a trend in addition to the intercept while pursuing the unit root tests for the Philippines Stock and consumer price indices. For the Consumer price index there not much to say since the graph for once more provides evidence that we should incorporate a trend into the

analysis. Contrary to the CPI for the stock index unit root test we should not include a time trend since there is not any short of trend in the graph of the variable.

Graph 19: Plot of the Philippines stock index.

Graph 19: Plot of the Philippines stock index.

In the next stage we will pursue the unit root tests for the Philippines stock index and CPI. Tables 19 and 20 provide the relevant tests.

Table 19: Unit Root Test for Philippines stock index

Unit root tests for variable LPHIL
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept but not a trend

*
17 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1998M2 to 1999M6

*

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.0856	10.7169	8.7169	7.8837	8.6341
ADF(1)	-1.9888*	13.1271	10.1271	8.8773*	10.0029
ADF(2)	-1.5486	13.1277	9.1277	7.4612	8.9620
ADF(3)	-1.5390	13.2763	8.2763	6.1933	8.0693
ADF(4)	-1.1362	13.3147	7.3147	4.8150	7.0662
ADF(5)	-1.4120	13.9614	6.9614	4.0451	6.6715
ADF(6)	-1.0434	14.0864	6.0864	2.7535	5.7551
ADF(7)	-1.1736	14.5396	5.5396	1.7901	5.1668
ADF(8)	-1.0222	14.5839	4.5839	.41788	4.1698
ADF(9)	-.94434	18.4588	7.4588	2.8762	7.0033
ADF(10)	-.61340	18.4782	6.4782	1.4789	5.9812
ADF(11)	-.71444	18.8959	5.8959	.48003	5.3576
ADF(12)	.11047	19.5196	5.5196	-.31284	4.9399

*

Table 20: Unit Root Test for Philippines Consumer's Price Index

Unit root tests for variable LCPI
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend

17 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1998M2 to 1999M6

*

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.7440*	61.0271	58.0271	56.7772*	57.9028
ADF(1)	-1.4227	61.0272	57.0272	55.3608	56.8616
ADF(2)	-1.2407	61.0824	56.0824	53.9994	55.8754
ADF(3)	-.81805	61.0825	55.0825	52.5828	54.8340
ADF(4)	.15501	62.1038	55.1038	52.1876	54.8139
ADF(5)	.29035	62.2400	54.2400	50.9071	53.9087
ADF(6)	.82354	63.3363	54.3363	50.5869	53.9636
ADF(7)	.68329	63.3396	53.3396	49.1735	52.9255
ADF(8)	.11785	63.9604	52.9604	48.3777	52.5049
ADF(9)	.25513	64.0789	52.0789	47.0796	51.5820
ADF(10)	-.54823	65.9324	52.9324	47.5166	52.3941
ADF(11)	-.58797	66.2585	52.2585	46.4260	51.6787
ADF(12)	-.60005	71.8286	56.8286	50.5795	56.2074

*

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = **-3.7119***
LL = Maximized log-likelihood AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

We cannot reject the null hypothesis of non stationarity for both variables. The absolute values of the ADF statistics are higher than the critical values for both variables.

Poland

The graphs 21 and 22 provided below describe the Polish stock and consumer price indices.

Graph 21: Polish Stock index

Graph 22: Polish Consumer Price index

We can see from graphs 21 and 22 that both variables have a very clear trend component and as such it is sensible to pursue the Unit root tests including a trend in addition to the intercept. Tables 21 and 22 describe the Unit root tests for the Polish stock and consumer price indices

Table 21: Unit Root Test of the Polish stock index

```

Unit root tests for variable LWARSAW
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend
*****
58 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1994M7 to 1999M4
*****

```

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-2.2107*	43.9252	40.9252	37.8346*	39.7214
ADF(1)	-1.7367	44.9523	40.9523	36.8314	39.3471
ADF(2)	-1.6547	44.9550	39.9550	34.8039	37.9485
ADF(3)	-1.6082	44.9554	38.9554	32.7740	36.5476
ADF(4)	-1.5214	45.1650	38.1650	30.9534	35.3559
ADF(5)	-1.5842	45.4282	37.4282	29.1864	34.2178
ADF(6)	-1.6800	45.6998	36.6998	27.4278	33.0881
ADF(7)	-2.2690	48.6826	38.6826	28.3804	34.6696
ADF(8)	-2.0236	48.7162	37.7162	26.3837	33.3020
ADF(9)	-2.7577	52.2793	40.2793	27.9167	35.4638
ADF(10)	-2.5548	52.2896	39.2896	25.8968	34.0728
ADF(11)	-3.1535	54.6803	40.6803	26.2572	35.0622
ADF(12)	-2.4684	55.2985	40.2985	24.8452	34.2791

```

*****
95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.4875*
LL = Maximized log-likelihood      AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion    HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

```

Table 22: Unit Root Test of the Polish Consumer Price Index

```

Unit root tests for variable LCPI
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend
*****
58 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.
Sample period from 1994M7 to 1999M4
*****

```

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-2.0832	196.4211	193.4211	190.3305	192.2172
ADF(1)	-2.7157	199.6152	195.6152	191.4943	194.0100
ADF(2)	-2.5603	200.7712	195.7712	190.6201	193.7647
ADF(3)	-2.6127	200.9666	194.9666	188.7852	192.5588
ADF(4)	-3.8041	208.9273	201.9273	194.7157	199.1182
ADF(5)	-3.4293	208.9273	200.9273	192.6855	197.7169
ADF(6)	-2.3389	210.9784	201.9784	192.7064	198.3668
ADF(7)	-2.2343	210.9860	200.9860	190.6838	196.9731
ADF(8)	-3.9597	224.1972	213.1972	201.8647	208.7829
ADF(9)	-3.1498	224.8389	212.8389	200.4763	208.0234
ADF(10)	-5.0972	234.4400	221.4400	208.0471	216.2232
ADF(11)	-4.9499	235.4690	221.4690	207.0459	215.8509
ADF(12)	-2.6374*	240.3374	225.3374	209.8841*	219.3180

```

*****
95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.4875*
LL = Maximized log-likelihood      AIC = Akaike Information Criterion
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion    HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion

```

In the case of Poland the results are similar with the data being such as that they do not allow us to reject the null hypothesis of non cointegration

Portugal

Graphs 23 and 24 provided below will determine whether we will use or not a trend in addition to the intercept while pursuing the Unit root tests.

Graph 23: Plot of the Lisbon stock index

Graph 24: Plot of the Portuguese Consumer's price index

We can see that for both variables there is a very strong evidence of a trend component which obliges us to use both an intercept and a trend while pursuing the unit root tests. Tables 23 and 24 provided below describe the unit root tests for the Lisbon stock index and the Portuguese consumer's price index.

Table 23: Unit root test for the Lisbon Stock Index

Unit root tests for variable LLISBO					
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend					

64 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.					
Sample period from 1994M3 to 1999M6					

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-1.8759*	91.5321	88.5321	85.2938*	87.2564
ADF(1)	-2.1031	93.2858	89.2858	84.9680	87.5848
ADF(2)	-2.1190	93.3594	88.3594	82.9622	86.2332
ADF(3)	-2.3207	94.1471	88.1471	81.6705	85.5957
ADF(4)	-2.0925	94.5553	87.5553	79.9992	84.5785
ADF(5)	-1.8779	95.1402	87.1402	78.5047	83.7383
ADF(6)	-1.9049	95.2614	86.2614	76.5464	82.4342
ADF(7)	-2.2163	96.9424	86.9424	76.1480	82.6899
ADF(8)	-2.3866	97.5071	86.5071	74.6332	81.8294
ADF(9)	-2.5150	97.9195	85.9195	72.9662	80.8166
ADF(10)	-2.8246	99.0571	86.0571	72.0243	80.5289
ADF(11)	-2.4834	99.1435	85.1435	70.0313	79.1901
ADF(12)	-2.4934	99.2940	84.2940	68.1023	77.9153

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.4801*					
LL = Maximized log-likelihood		AIC = Akaike Information Criterion			
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion		HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion			

For once again we find no evidence not to reject the null hypothesis of non-stationarity for both variables since the absolute value of the Augmented Dickey Fuller tests is greater than the correspondent statistic for both variables $|ADF - statistic| > |test - statistic|$ -. We can proceed and say with certainty that the variables are not I(1).

Table 24: Unit root test for the Portuguese Consumer's Price Index

Unit root tests for variable LCPI					
The Dickey-Fuller regressions include an intercept and a linear trend					

63 observations used in the estimation of all ADF regressions.					
Sample period from 1994M3 to 1999M5					

	Test Statistic	LL	AIC	SBC	HQC
DF	-2.3486*	280.6425	277.6425	274.4278*	276.3781
ADF(1)	-2.7543	282.9118	278.9118	274.6255	277.2259
ADF(2)	-2.4521	283.4164	278.4164	273.0585	276.3091
ADF(3)	-2.2484	283.7571	277.7571	271.3277	275.2284
ADF(4)	-2.1859	283.8150	276.8150	269.3140	273.8648
ADF(5)	-2.1589	284.3464	276.3464	267.7739	272.9748
ADF(6)	-2.1878	285.1290	276.1290	266.4849	272.3359
ADF(7)	-2.1162	287.0557	277.0557	266.3400	272.8412
ADF(8)	-2.1917	288.0560	277.0560	265.2687	272.4200
ADF(9)	-2.2737	288.5893	276.5893	263.7305	271.5319
ADF(10)	-2.8191	292.9295	279.9295	265.9992	274.4506
ADF(11)	-2.5440	293.1075	279.1075	264.1056	273.2072
ADF(12)	-2.2210	293.9491	278.9491	262.8756	272.6273

95% critical value for the augmented Dickey-Fuller statistic = -3.4812*					
LL = Maximized log-likelihood		AIC = Akaike Information Criterion			
SBC = Schwarz Bayesian Criterion		HQC = Hannan-Quinn Criterion			

3.5 Conclusion.

We have established in the previous section that none of the variables is stationary since not even a single one of the unit root tests revealed the opposite testing them under a lag choice of 12- which is natural to assume in our case in order to allow for the short term dynamics. Let us discuss the implications of our findings by pointing out some characteristics that the Fisher equation is imposing in terms of econometric theory. If stocks provide a good hedge against inflation as it is supposed by the Fisher equation then stock prices and goods prices should be cointegrated. When variables are cointegrated their long term trends adjust to an equilibrium constraint. Deviations of these series from their equilibrium values are transitory in nature and are appropriately modelled in the structure of Error-Correction Models. Paying a close attention to the plots given above we don't see any clear evidence that the variables are stationary in most cases. We should also establish here the fact that for a choice of a smaller lag e.g. 4 which would make more of a sense if we had quarterly data we

find that the data can be described as a mixed bag since in some cases we find that we can reject the null hypothesis of non stationarity for the variables that capture the stock index. In other words for a shorter horizon we find that there might be a case for stationary variables. On the other hand we cannot proceed with a cointegration technique unless all the variables are stationary. So in either cases a cointegration analysis is not the suggested way someone should utilize.

The sensible choice then under this framework it to proceed with an ARDL approach to the Error Correction Model (ECM)-Pesaran- which imposes no restrictions for the data in terms of stationarity. In other words it can be used irrespectively of whether the data are $I(0)$ or $I(1)$. In any case this is the appropriate way to go assuming also that the unit root tests-residual based tests-(Pesaran) can be misleading- and as such not valid- under certain circumstances due to residuals autocorrelation. Following the ARDL approach we can overcome any potential problems derived from any potential biasness from the unit root tests without the need of a Johansen test for establishing for sure cointegration. Let us here remind to ourselves that a Johansen test in any case would have been the wrong thing to do since we don't see any evidence of stationarity from our data. There seems to be no other viable root for the analysis except the ARDL approach to the Error-Correction Model.

Chapter IV

4.1 ARDL approach to ECM.

The ARDL procedure involves two stages. We will first pursue an F-statistic in order to establish whether there exists a long run relationship between the variables. This is tested by computing the F-statistic for testing the significance of the lagged levels of the variables in the Error Correction form of the underlying ARDL model. The asymptotic distribution of this F-statistic is non-standard and Pesaran has tabulated the appropriate critical values . One set of values assumes that all variables are I(0) while the other assumes that all variables are I(1). If the F-statistic falls outside the band suggested by the above distribution then a conclusive decision can be made without needing to know whether the variables fall within the I(0) or I(1) category. If otherwise we will be using the unit root tests provided in the previous section to establish whether the variables are I(0) or I(1) and in our case we have already establish that we cannot reject the null hypothesis of non-cointegration for any of the variables at least at a 12 lag framework.

The second and final stage of the analysis is to estimate the coefficients of the long run relations and make inferences about their values using an ARDL approach. For this second stage to be valid we must first ensure that the first stage of the F-statistic is fully satisfied. Let us now proceed by applying the above analysis to our data.

4.2 The Davidson, Hendry, Srba and Yeo Model

Davidson, Hendry, Srba and Yeo developed a highly influential model- Economic Journal 1978- of the national consumption-income relationship. The model is essentially the same for our case too since in the long run it imposes a unit long run elasticity just like the Fisher model. In more detail let us examine the original model below:

$$c = Ky$$

the basic Error Correction Model equation is:

$$\Delta \log c_t = \mathbf{b}\Delta \log y_t + \mathbf{g}(\log y_{t-q} - \log c_{t-1}) + u_t$$

Note here that the model imposes unit long-run elasticity.

The model is of high significance for our analysis and it will be described below adjusted for the Fisher equation.

The long run equilibrium of the Fisher equation is :

$$\Delta P_t = \mathbf{b}\Delta I_t + \mathbf{e}_t$$

or in other words :

$$\log P_t - \log I_t = \log \mathbf{b}$$

As such the model's Error Correction Model equation becomes:

$$\Delta \log P_t = \mathbf{b}\Delta \log CPI_t + \mathbf{g}(\log CPI_{t-1} - \log P_{t-1}) + u_t$$

The equation above is the Error Correction Model representation of the Fisher effect, it is in fact the equation we will be examining in order to establish the relationship between equity returns and inflation. In the next section we will outline the results of the ARDL method for each country and we will also establish an implementation of the results.

4.3 Error Correction Model Results.

As noted previously the ARDL procedure has the first step of establishing the long run relationship between the variables utilising the F-statistics and the second stage, after the long run relationship has been established, is to find the actual magnitude of the relationship through the ARDL procedure.

Argentina

The F-statistics band for the case of Argentina are provided below , and the long run relationship which could not be examined under the procedure suggested by Johansen since we found contradictory empirical evidence in relation to the stationarity of the variables is confirmed by the F-statistics. More details are provided in tables 1 and 2 provided below:

Table 1: F-statistic for DLMERVAL

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLMERVAL			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LCPI(-1)		LMERVAL(-1)
58 observations used for estimation from 1994M9 to 1999M6			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	11.4351	36.7299	.31133[.758]
DLMERVAL(-1)	.22614	.20410	1.1080[.276]
DLMERVAL(-2)	-.15938	.19461	-.81894[.419]
DLMERVAL(-3)	.070714	.20616	.34301[.734]
DLMERVAL(-4)	.016710	.19336	.086419[.932]
DLMERVAL(-5)	.27182	.18729	1.4513[.157]
DLMERVAL(-6)	-.19529	.19579	-.99747[.326]
DLMERVAL(-7)	.25047	.19276	1.2994[.203]
DLMERVAL(-8)	-.023018	.16953	-.13577[.893]
DLMERVAL(-9)	.18584	.17491	1.0625[.296]
DLMERVAL(-10)	.31769	.16491	1.9264[.063]
DLMERVAL(-11)	-.29777	.22034	-1.3514[.186]
DLMERVAL(-12)	-.0052273	.23017	-.022711[.982]
DLCPI(-1)	-17.9972	5.8501	-3.0764[.004]
DLCPI(-2)	7.0698	6.0545	1.1677[.252]
DLCPI(-3)	-4.3357	6.0470	-.71699[.479]
DLCPI(-4)	.52504	6.0754	.086420[.932]
DLCPI(-5)	-9.5971	5.9579	-1.6108[.117]
DLCPI(-6)	8.7975	6.1808	1.4234[.165]
DLCPI(-7)	-8.5486	6.7651	-1.2636[.216]
DLCPI(-8)	4.0508	6.8323	.59290[.558]
DLCPI(-9)	-12.6717	7.1437	-1.7738[.086]
DLCPI(-10)	12.6657	7.3826	1.7156[.096]
DLCPI(-11)	-8.4385	7.4286	-1.1360[.265]
DLCPI(-12)	1.0584	6.8068	.15549[.877]
LCPI(-1)	-.81038	2.9243	-.27712[.784]
LMERVAL(-1)	-.17927	.12979	-1.3812[.177]

Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	5.1387[.077]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	5.3807[.068]	
F Statistic	F(2, 31)=	1.5068[.237]	

Table 2: F-statistic for DLCPI

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLCPI			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LCPI(-1)	LMERVAL(-1)	
58 observations used for estimation from 1994M9 to 1999M6			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	3.1067	.96250	3.2277[.003]
DLMERVAL(-1)	-.0076531	.0053484	-1.4309[.162]
DLMERVAL(-2)	-.010959	.0050998	-2.1489[.040]
DLMERVAL(-3)	-.0082312	.0054022	-1.5237[.138]
DLMERVAL(-4)	-.0042042	.0050669	-.82975[.413]
DLMERVAL(-5)	-.013195	.0049079	-2.6885[.011]
DLMERVAL(-6)	-.0040258	.0051305	-.78468[.439]
DLMERVAL(-7)	-.0089791	.0050512	-1.7776[.085]
DLMERVAL(-8)	-.0067525	.0044426	-1.5199[.139]
DLMERVAL(-9)	.0014477	.0045834	.31585[.754]
DLMERVAL(-10)	-.0083059	.0043215	-1.9220[.064]
DLMERVAL(-11)	-.0058219	.0057740	-1.0083[.321]
DLMERVAL(-12)	-.0035680	.0060316	-.59155[.558]
DLCPI(-1)	.14457	.15330	.94306[.353]
DLCPI(-2)	-.30393	.15866	-1.9156[.065]
DLCPI(-3)	-.033759	.15846	-.21304[.833]
DLCPI(-4)	-.039755	.15921	-.24971[.804]
DLCPI(-5)	-.16165	.15613	-1.0354[.308]
DLCPI(-6)	.27020	.16197	1.6682[.105]
DLCPI(-7)	-.11133	.17728	-.62797[.535]
DLCPI(-8)	-.085548	.17904	-.47782[.636]
DLCPI(-9)	-.0085915	.18720	-.045895[.964]
DLCPI(-10)	-.22560	.19346	-1.1662[.252]
DLCPI(-11)	.071394	.19466	.36676[.716]
DLCPI(-12)	.030881	.17837	.17313[.864]
LCPI(-1)	-.24915	.076631	-3.2513[.003]
LMERVAL(-1)	.0086606	.0034011	2.5464[.016]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 16.0841[.000]		
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 18.8371[.000]		
F Statistic	F(2, 31)= 5.9477[.007]		

The range provided by Pesaran for this distribution of the F-statistic for 2 variables is for I(0) 3.795 and for I(1) 4.855. We can see that we don't need to recall the unit root tests provided in chapter 3 in order to continue the analysis since both F-statistics in the case of Argentina fall outside the band provided by Pesaran. In other words we can proceed with the ARDL approach to the Error Correction Model without any hesitations.

The next table-table 3- provides the Error Correction Model for the case of Argentina, using the Schwartz- Bayesian statistics and again using a 12-lag framework as we did for the unit root tests in chapter 3. We can see that our data now fit much better than in the simple OLS case giving us higher R^2 for both the simple and the adjusted for degrees of freedom cases. We also find that we obtain statistically significant ECM coefficient with the correct sign-that is a minus-. The ECM coefficient reveals a

moderate speed of convergence to equilibrium after the system has been somehow shocked. Let us remind ourselves the ECM representation of the model:

$$\Delta \log P_t = \beta \Delta \log CPI_t + \alpha (\log CPI_{t-1} - \log P_{t-1}) + u_t$$

in other words the table below reveals that :

$$\Delta \log P_t = 0.064568(0.032755) \Delta \log CPI_t - 0.13029(0.065294) (\log I_{t-1} - \log P_{t-1})$$

Table 3: ECM for Argentina

Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model			
ARDL(1,0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion			

Dependent variable is dLMERVAL			
59 observations used for estimation from 1994M8 to 1999M6			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
dLCPI	.064568	.032755	1.9713[.054]
ecm(-1)	-.13029	.065924	-1.9763[.053]

List of additional temporary variables created:			
dLMERVAL = LMERVAL-LMERVAL(-1)			
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)			
ecm = LMERVAL -.49558*LCPI			

R-Squared	.064131	R-Bar-Squared	.047712
S.E. of Regression	.11906	F-Stat.	F(1, 57) 3.9060[.053]
Mean of Dependent Variable	-.0015206	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.12200
Residual Sum of Squares	.80797	Equation Log-likelihood	42.8604
Akaike Info. Criterion	40.8604	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	38.7829
DW-statistic	1.8850		

R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable			
dLMERVAL and in cases where the error correction model is highly			
restricted, these measures could become negative.			

The above equation indicates that there is a positive relationship between stock returns and inflation, of a magnitude 0.49558. This is in contrast with the a priori expectations from the Economic theory as this is suggested by Irving Fisher since according to the Fisher effect we should have got a positive-which we have-relationship of approximately 1. Summarising for Argentina we can say that although a long run relationship is indicated by our data and the respective F-statistics- in a sense cointegration is present-, this is definitely not the one he have been expecting according to the Economic Theory as this is outlined by Irving Fisher. Nevertheless it is proven by the above results that there might be a case for a Fisher effect, at least in

terms of the direction of the relationship. Possible explanations for the results include the fact that the market might not be discounting the inflation data efficiently. Of course this is contrasted with the theory of rational expectations and the Efficient Market Hypothesis. Other reasons of course include the fact that there might be a problem with the fact that we have not taken into consideration all possible variables that might affect the results. Let us proceed and examine the Brazilian data.

Brazil

Following exactly the same procedure for Brazil we yield the F-statistics tables – tables 4 & 5:

Table 4:F-statistic for DLBOVESPA

<i>Variable Addition Test (OLS case)</i>			
<i>Dependent variable is DLBOVESPA</i>			
<i>List of the variables added to the regression:</i>			
	<i>LCPI(-1)</i>	<i>LBOVESPA(-1)</i>	
44 observations used for estimation from 1995M11 to 1999M6			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	7.1714	15.2490	.47028[.644]
DLBOVESPA(-1)	.20056	.28148	.71252[.486]
DLBOVESPA(-2)	.25557	.22516	1.1350[.272]
DLBOVESPA(-3)	.33102	.20300	1.6306[.121]
DLBOVESPA(-4)	.50906	.20391	2.4965[.023]
DLBOVESPA(-5)	.077450	.22437	.34519[.734]
DLBOVESPA(-6)	.038652	.22786	.16963[.867]
DLBOVESPA(-7)	.35085	.20224	1.7348[.101]
DLBOVESPA(-8)	.37289	.22266	1.6747[.112]
DLBOVESPA(-9)	.39312	.23306	1.6868[.110]
DLBOVESPA(-10)	.55263	.23524	2.3492[.031]
DLBOVESPA(-11)	-.13236	.26343	-.50245[.622]
DLBOVESPA(-12)	.16772	.25884	.64798[.526]
DLCPPI(-1)	5.1726	7.4219	.69693[.495]
DLCPPI(-2)	8.6052	8.9407	.96247[.349]
DLCPPI(-3)	-5.3076	8.8201	-.60175[.555]
DLCPPI(-4)	-1.8767	8.0892	-.23200[.819]
DLCPPI(-5)	-8.3690	8.5673	-.97685[.342]
DLCPPI(-6)	14.4130	8.5383	1.6880[.110]
DLCPPI(-7)	-26.1681	9.2484	-2.8295[.012]
DLCPPI(-8)	4.1499	10.8264	.38332[.706]
DLCPPI(-9)	-16.8349	8.8890	-1.8939[.075]
DLCPPI(-10)	3.6634	9.1226	.40158[.693]
DLCPPI(-11)	-8.3527	8.6418	-.96654[.347]
DLCPPI(-12)	-.99062	7.8446	-.12628[.901]
LCPI(-1)	-.12371	1.9205	-.064417[.949]
LBOVESPA(-1)	-.67377	.29579	-2.2779[.036]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 11.2279[.004]		
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 12.9629[.002]		
F Statistic	F(2, 17)= 2.9121[.082]		

Table 5:F-statistic for DLCPI

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)-Dependent variable is DLCPI			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LCPI(-1)	LBOVESPA(-1)	
43 observations used for estimation from 1995M11 to 1999M5			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	1.3400	.44674	2.9995[.008]
DLBOVESPA(-1)	-.0029714	.0081195	-.36596[.719]
DLBOVESPA(-2)	-.0046962	.0067179	-.69906[.495]
DLBOVESPA(-3)	-.7083E-3	.0061768	-.11467[.910]
DLBOVESPA(-4)	-.0033366	.0057083	-.58452[.567]
DLBOVESPA(-5)	.3684E-3	.0063713	.057819[.955]
DLBOVESPA(-6)	-.0071589	.0063649	-1.1247[.277]
DLBOVESPA(-7)	-.014298	.0060947	-2.3460[.032]
DLBOVESPA(-8)	-.0085549	.0072424	-1.1812[.255]
DLBOVESPA(-9)	-.0088676	.0072036	-1.2310[.236]
DLBOVESPA(-10)	-.6233E-3	.0065711	-.094852[.926]
DLBOVESPA(-11)	.0019186	.0075247	.25497[.802]
DLBOVESPA(-12)	-.1591E-3	.0072348	-.021997[.983]
DLCPPI(-1)	.50323	.21092	2.3859[.030]
DLCPPI(-2)	-.27788	.25054	-1.1091[.284]
DLCPPI(-3)	.12778	.24809	.51504[.614]
DLCPPI(-4)	-.40826	.23374	-1.7466[.100]
DLCPPI(-5)	-.014163	.23978	-.059068[.954]
DLCPPI(-6)	-.31952	.24039	-1.3292[.202]
DLCPPI(-7)	-.082604	.25862	-.31940[.754]
DLCPPI(-8)	-.43895	.30315	-1.4480[.167]
DLCPPI(-9)	.11537	.25110	.45947[.652]
DLCPPI(-10)	-.34346	.25524	-1.3457[.197]
DLCPPI(-11)	-.049106	.24478	-.20062[.844]
DLCPPI(-12)	.047066	.21914	.21478[.833]
LCPI(-1)	-.17879	.057843	-3.0909[.007]
LBOVESPA(-1)	-.0034342	.0086335	-.39778[.696]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	16.1404[.000]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	20.2348[.000]	
F Statistic	F(2, 16)=	4.8073[.023]	

We can see that in this case we cannot yield whether there exists a long run relationship between the variables since the F-statistic, which considers the lagged variables effect in the case where the logged difference of CPI is examined, is below the upper bound critical value. We must recall the unit root test in chapter 3 for the Log of the CPI and decide whether or not to proceed. Recalling back the unit root test it reveals that the LCPI variable can be considered as an I(0) variables by definition then the F-statistic provided by Pesaran in the case of the I(0) is 3.793 which means that we can reject the hypothesis of non significance of the lagged variables into the analysis. In conclusion we can proceed with the ARDL approach to the ECM. The next table provides the details of the analysis-table 6:

Table 6:ECM for Brazil

```

Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model
ARDL(1,0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion
*****
Dependent variable is dLBOVESPA
44 observations used for estimation from 1995M10 to 1999M5
*****
Regressor          Coefficient          Standard Error          T-Ratio[Prob]
dLCPI              .17055                .087700                1.9447[.059]
ecm(-1)           -.13564               .070838                -1.9147[.062]
*****
List of additional temporary variables created:
dLBOVESPA = LBOVESPA-LBOVESPA(-1)
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)
ecm = LBOVESPA -1.2574*LCPI
*****
R-Squared          .080228      R-Bar-Squared          .058328
S.E. of Regression .12826      F-Stat.      F( 1, 42)      3.6635[.062]
Mean of Dependent Variable .019654      S.D. of Dependent Variable .13217
Residual Sum of Squares .69088      Equation Log-likelihood      28.9541
Akaike Info. Criterion 26.9541      Schwarz Bayesian Criterion      25.1699
DW-statistic      2.1769
*****
R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable
dLBOVESPA and in cases where the error correction model is highly
restricted, these measures could become negative.

```

We find highly statistically significant results in the case of Brazil. The ECM coefficient is negative in other words it has the right sign and it shows a rather moderate speed of convergence to equilibrium since it only accounts for -.13564. we should point out here that the larger the absolute value of the ECM higher the speed of convergence to the equilibrium state after the system has been shocked . The data fit much better than in the OLS case to our analysis and the R^2 values are even higher from the previous case of Argentina. What about the Fisher effect then? In this case we see that the Fisher effect is present from the equation indicated from the ECM the logarithm of the Consumer Price Index is positive and this time this positive effect is even higher. In fact it is not statistically different from 1 as we saw in the previous table. It is very evident in the case of Brazil the Fisher effect. We can see that the utilisation of the ECM analysis has already yielded highly significant results in terms of justifying the economic theory. Next country in our analysis is Chile.

Chile

The same procedure will yield us the F-statistics provided in the tables 7 and 8 below:

Table 7: F-statistic for DLIGPA

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)
Dependent variable is DLCPI
List of the variables added to the regression:
 LCPI(-1) LIGPA(-1)

52 observations used for estimation from 1995M2 to 1999M5

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.10269	.094526	1.0863[.288]
DLIGPA(-1)	-.0037011	.010360	-.35723[.724]
DLIGPA(-2)	-.020066	.011225	-1.7876[.086]
DLIGPA(-3)	-.014058	.011993	-1.1722[.252]
DLIGPA(-4)	-.0058084	.011214	-.51797[.609]
DLIGPA(-5)	.0079396	.011590	.68503[.500]
DLIGPA(-6)	-.0044363	.010041	-.44182[.662]
DLIGPA(-7)	-.0058909	.010647	-.55330[.585]
DLIGPA(-8)	-.0034312	.011756	-.29185[.773]
DLIGPA(-9)	-.0054950	.011372	-.48320[.633]
DLIGPA(-10)	.016294	.012007	1.3571[.187]
DLIGPA(-11)	.0032520	.011212	.29006[.774]
DLIGPA(-12)	.016175	.010894	1.4847[.150]
DLCPI(-1)	-.15048	.17940	-.83881[.410]
DLCPI(-2)	-.22730	.18578	-1.2235[.233]
DLCPI(-3)	-.32468	.17938	-1.8100[.082]
DLCPI(-4)	-.42490	.20117	-2.1121[.045]
DLCPI(-5)	-.44319	.20835	-2.1271[.043]
DLCPI(-6)	-.27442	.22340	-1.2284[.231]
DLCPI(-7)	-.38300	.21259	-1.8016[.084]
DLCPI(-8)	-.11956	.23436	-.51016[.614]
DLCPI(-9)	-.21378	.19897	-1.0744[.293]
DLCPI(-10)	-.36797	.18956	-1.9412[.064]
DLCPI(-11)	-.072271	.19175	-.37690[.709]
DLCPI(-12)	.11867	.18684	.63515[.531]
LCPI(-1)	-.038750	.021947	-1.7656[.090]
LIGPA(-1)	.010726	.0060892	1.7614[.090]

Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:
 Lagrange Multiplier Statistic CHSQ(2)= 7.7482[.021]
 Likelihood Ratio Statistic CHSQ(2)= 8.3901[.015]

F Statistic **F(2, 25)= 2.1887[.133]**

Table 8: F-statistic for DLCPI

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)-Dependent variable is DLCPI
List of the variables added to the regression:
 LCPI(-1) LIGPA(-1)

52 observations used for estimation from 1995M2 to 1999M5

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
A	.10269	.094526	1.0863[.288]
DLIGPA(-1)	-.0037011	.010360	-.35723[.724]
DLIGPA(-2)	-.020066	.011225	-1.7876[.086]
DLIGPA(-3)	-.014058	.011993	-1.1722[.252]
DLIGPA(-4)	-.0058084	.011214	-.51797[.609]
DLIGPA(-5)	.0079396	.011590	.68503[.500]
DLIGPA(-6)	-.0044363	.010041	-.44182[.662]
DLIGPA(-7)	-.0058909	.010647	-.55330[.585]
DLIGPA(-8)	-.0034312	.011756	-.29185[.773]
DLIGPA(-9)	-.0054950	.011372	-.48320[.633]
DLIGPA(-10)	.016294	.012007	1.3571[.187]
DLIGPA(-11)	.0032520	.011212	.29006[.774]
DLIGPA(-12)	.016175	.010894	1.4847[.150]
DLCPI(-1)	-.15048	.17940	-.83881[.410]
DLCPI(-2)	-.22730	.18578	-1.2235[.233]
DLCPI(-3)	-.32468	.17938	-1.8100[.082]
DLCPI(-4)	-.42490	.20117	-2.1121[.045]
DLCPI(-5)	-.44319	.20835	-2.1271[.043]
DLCPI(-6)	-.27442	.22340	-1.2284[.231]
DLCPI(-7)	-.38300	.21259	-1.8016[.084]
DLCPI(-8)	-.11956	.23436	-.51016[.614]
DLCPI(-9)	-.21378	.19897	-1.0744[.293]
DLCPI(-10)	-.36797	.18956	-1.9412[.064]
DLCPI(-11)	-.072271	.19175	-.37690[.709]
DLCPI(-12)	.11867	.18684	.63515[.531]
LCPI(-1)	-.038750	.021947	-1.7656[.090]
LIGPA(-1)	.010726	.0060892	1.7614[.090]

Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:
 Lagrange Multiplier Statistic CHSQ(2)= 7.7482[.021]
 Likelihood Ratio Statistic CHSQ(2)= 8.3901[.015]

F Statistic **F(2, 25)= 2.1887[.133]**

We can see that both these F-statistics are outside of the bound suggested by Pesaran which is 3.793-they are well below which in other words can be discounted as that we can proceed to the second stage of the ARDL analysis, since as we have already mentioned it is a prerequisite to satisfy this stage. The ECM is provided below in table -9:

Table 9:ECM for Chile

<i>Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model</i>			
<i>ARDL(1,0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion</i>			

<i>Dependent variable is dLIGPA</i>			
<i>53 observations used for estimation from 1995M1 to 1999M5</i>			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
dLCPI	.031069	.054110	.57419[.568]
<i>ecm(-1)</i>	<i>-.016895</i>	<i>.028653</i>	<i>-.58965[.558]</i>

List of additional temporary variables created:			
dLIGPA = LIGPA-LIGPA(-1)			
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)			
ecm = LIGPA -1.8390*LCPI			

R-Squared	.0068511	R-Bar-Squared	-.012622
S.E. of Regression	.060242	F-Stat. F(1, 51)	.35182[.556]
Mean of Dependent Variable	-.0036503	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.059865
Residual Sum of Squares	.18508	Equation Log-likelihood	74.7134
Akaike Info. Criterion	72.7134	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	70.7431
DW-statistic	1.9281		

R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable			
dLIGPA and in cases where the error correction model is highly			
restricted, these measures could become negative.			

We can see from table 9 that the results for the case of Chile are not significant since the t-statistics are pretty low. The fitness of the data is again very little in fact it is statistically insignificant. The ECM term has the right sign and it shows a moderate speed of adjustment to equilibrium. The relationship between the change in the logarithm of the stock and the consumer index is positive and it is approximately equal to 2. Summarizing for Chile we should say that the results should not be considered very carefully since they don't provide any stable framework of analysis due to their lack of significance. Nevertheless we can say that the results show an over adjustment for potentially inflationary pressures. This can be justified by examining the historical evidence in terms of inflation for Chile. Chile has had a big inflation

problem for many years, we can say then that this kind of over adjustment can be found in economies with very high inflation. Let us proceed by examining the empirical evidence for some European countries.

Czech Republic

Tables 10 and 11 provide us the F-statistics for the significance of the lagged variables, in other words they provide us the framework to examine whether there exists a possible long run relationship between the variables, that will allow us to proceed to the next stage.

Table 10:F-statistic for LPX50

<i>Variable Addition Test (OLS case)</i>			
<i>Dependent variable is DLPX50</i>			
<i>List of the variables added to the regression:</i>			
	<i>LPX50(-1)</i>	<i>LCPI(-1)</i>	
50 observations used for estimation from 1995M5 to 1999M6			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	1905.0	684.7622	2.7820[.009]
DLPX50(-1)	.34749	.18885	1.8400[.075]
DLPX50(-2)	.032294	.17842	.18100[.858]
DLPX50(-3)	.094263	.18414	.51191[.612]
DLPX50(-4)	.061248	.17945	.34130[.735]
DLPX50(-5)	.18812	.19474	.96598[.342]
DLPX50(-6)	.29468	.17584	1.6758[.104]
DLPX50(-7)	.26485	.17396	1.5225[.138]
DLPX50(-8)	.17542	.17566	.99863[.326]
DLPX50(-9)	-.027758	.18396	-.15089[.881]
DLPX50(-10)	.28036	.18137	1.5458[.132]
DLPX50(-11)	.19338	.22565	.85697[.398]
DLPX50(-12)	.12424	.18102	.68632[.498]
DLCPI(-1)	319.2005	803.3883	.39732[.694]
DLCPI(-2)	900.9069	776.6852	1.1599[.255]
DLCPI(-3)	680.4886	789.6577	.86175[.395]
DLCPI(-4)	221.7174	775.1089	.28605[.777]
LPX50(-1)	-226.9327	80.7555	-2.8101[.009]
LCPI(-1)	-105.7311	62.4458	-1.6932[.100]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 10.4081[.005]		
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 11.6700[.003]		
F Statistic	F(2, 31)= 4.0747[.027]		

Table 11:F-statistic for LCPI

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLCPI			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LPX50(-1)	LCPI(-1)	
50 observations used for estimation from 1995M5 to 1999M6			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	-.088993	.14505	-.61355[.544]
DLPX50(-1)	-.2599E-4	.4000E-4	-.64975[.521]
DLPX50(-2)	-.5744E-4	.3779E-4	-1.5198[.139]
DLPX50(-3)	-.3838E-4	.3900E-4	-.98390[.333]
DLPX50(-4)	-.3298E-4	.3801E-4	-.86754[.392]
DLPX50(-5)	.6263E-4	.4125E-4	1.5183[.139]
DLPX50(-6)	.2402E-4	.3725E-4	.64492[.524]
DLPX50(-7)	.2771E-4	.3685E-4	.75192[.458]
DLPX50(-8)	-.7174E-4	.3721E-4	-1.9280[.063]
DLPX50(-9)	-.1999E-4	.3897E-4	-.51289[.612]
DLPX50(-10)	-.6934E-4	.3842E-4	-1.8050[.081]
DLPX50(-11)	.9543E-4	.4780E-4	1.9965[.055]
DLPX50(-12)	-.5200E-4	.3834E-4	-1.3562[.185]
DLCPI(-1)	.063279	.17017	.37185[.713]
DLCPI(-2)	-.073030	.16452	-.44391[.660]
DLCPI(-3)	.21463	.16726	1.2832[.209]
DLCPI(-4)	-.13770	.16418	-.83869[.408]
LPX50(-1)	.021164	.017106	1.2373[.225]
LCPI(-1)	-.0075333	.013227	-.56953[.573]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	4.5190[.104]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	4.7364[.094]	
F Statistic	F(2, 31)=	1.5401[.230]	

Again similar conclusions with the procedure for Chile the F-statistic for the Stock Index falls within the band set by Pesaran which means that we need to recall the unit root test from the previous stage of the analysis. The unit root test revealed that the PX50 variable is an I(0) variable. According to this and the fact that the F-statistic's absolute value-4.0747- is greater than the respective value for the I(0) variable indicated by the lower bound of the distribution tabulated by Pesaran-3.793- we conclude that we can continue by utilizing the ARDL procedure to the ECM . There are no such problems with the F-statistic for the LCPI variable and a decision can be taken irrespectively if the underlying variable is I(0) or I(1). The F-statistic for the LCPI variable is 1.5401 which is well below the lower bound of the F-statistic bound we are imposed. In conclusion and with the help of the unit root test for LX50 we can proceed with the ARDL which is outlined in the table below table 12:

Table 12: ECM for Czech Republic

```

Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model
      ARDL(1,0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion
*****
Dependent variable is dLPX50
51 observations used for estimation from 1995M4 to 1999M6
*****
Regressor              Coefficient          Standard Error          T-Ratio[Prob]
dLCPI                  .071396              .064781                 1.1021[.276]
ecm(-1)                -.055759             .051078                 -1.0916[.280]
*****
List of additional temporary variables created:
dLPX50 = LPX50-LPX50(-1)
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)
ecm = LPX50 -1.2804*LCPI
*****
R-Squared              .023652              R-Bar-Squared          .0037260
S.E. of Regression     .073977              F-Stat.      F( 1, 49)    1.1870[.281]
Mean of Dependent Variable .0035448            S.D. of Dependent Variable .074115
Residual Sum of Squares .26816              Equation Log-likelihood 61.4584
Akaike Info. Criterion 59.4584            Schwarz Bayesian Criterion 57.5266
DW-statistic          1.7970
*****
R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable
dLPX50 and in cases where the error correction model is highly
restricted, these measures could become negative.

```

The values of the ARDL are again not highly significant in the case of the Czech Republic. The R^2 values are low if we compare them with the ones from Brazil or Argentina, but nevertheless there is exhibited a relationship between the two variables. The relationship is again positive and it's magnitude is around 1.2. The ECM coefficient reveals a relatively low speed to adjustment after a potential shock. As for the Fisher effect again it is somehow present in the this case too since our coefficients are not statistically far way from the ones suggested by the Fisher equation.

Greece

The F-statistics are provided below in order to establish whether there exist any significant effects from the lagged variables and whether there exists any long run relationship for the variables-Tables 13 and 14-.

Table 13:F-statistic for DLATHENSGE

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLATHENS			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
LATHENSGE(-1) LCPI(-1)			
50 observations used for estimation from 1995M5 to 1999M6			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	1.0264	2.8058	.36583[.718]
DLATHENS(-1)	-.16612	.21589	-.76950[.449]
DLATHENS(-2)	-.18918	.20925	-.90407[.375]
DLATHENS(-3)	-.22721	.20692	-1.0980[.284]
DLATHENS(-4)	-.25734	.18498	-1.3912[.177]
DLATHENS(-5)	-.62103	.19847	-3.1291[.005]
DLATHENS(-6)	-.42300	.23158	-1.8266[.081]
DLATHENS(-7)	-.12101	.21577	-.56086[.580]
DLATHENS(-8)	-.078723	.18755	-.41974[.679]
DLATHENS(-9)	-.44832	.18172	-2.4671[.021]
DLATHENS(-10)	-.18261	.20710	-.88175[.387]
DLATHENS(-11)	-.43070	.22256	-1.9353[.065]
DLATHENS(-12)	-.19797	.23128	-.85596[.401]
DLCPI(-1)	-1.5332	3.9537	-.38778[.702]
DLCPI(-2)	-7.5668	3.8812	-1.9496[.064]
DLCPI(-3)	-1.9493	4.0978	-.47569[.639]
DLCPI(-4)	-3.7720	3.8576	-.97782[.338]
DLCPI(-5)	-4.7474	3.8261	-1.2408[.227]
DLCPI(-6)	-6.6040	3.6655	-1.8016[.085]
DLCPI(-7)	-6.9936	3.9182	-1.7849[.087]
DLCPI(-8)	-4.2822	4.0901	-1.0470[.306]
DLCPI(-9)	-5.8137	3.9590	-1.4685[.156]
DLCPI(-10)	-6.0897	4.2757	-1.4243[.168]
DLCPI(-11)	-3.8367	4.3348	-.88508[.385]
DLCPI(-12)	-4.8413	4.6087	-1.0505[.304]
LATHENSGE(-1)	-.028815	.094541	-.30479[.763]
LCPI(-1)	-.084666	.58449	-.14485[.886]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	.33314[.847]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	.33425[.846]	
F Statistic		F(2, 23)=	.077135[.926]

Table 14:F-statistic for DLCPI

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLCPI			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
LATHENSGE(-1) LCPI(-1)			
50 observations used for estimation from 1995M5 to 1999M6			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.12280	.10955	1.1210[.274]
DLATHENS(-1)	.0076568	.0084291	.90838[.373]
DLATHENS(-2)	.0020960	.0081700	.25655[.800]
DLATHENS(-3)	-.0045412	.0080791	-.56209[.579]
DLATHENS(-4)	-.0024883	.0072223	-.34453[.734]
DLATHENS(-5)	.9065E-3	.0077492	.11698[.908]
DLATHENS(-6)	.0046639	.0090417	.51582[.611]
DLATHENS(-7)	-.0016121	.0084245	-.19136[.850]
DLATHENS(-8)	-.0037959	.0073229	-.51836[.609]
DLATHENS(-9)	.0025848	.0070951	.36431[.719]
DLATHENS(-10)	.0089249	.0080859	1.1037[.281]
DLATHENS(-11)	.0072964	.0086895	.83967[.410]
DLATHENS(-12)	-.0021862	.0090304	-.24209[.811]
DLCPI(-1)	-.040503	.15437	-.26238[.795]
DLCPI(-2)	-.21964	.15154	-1.4494[.161]
DLCPI(-3)	.078326	.15999	.48955[.629]
DLCPI(-4)	-.11166	.15062	-.74133[.466]
DLCPI(-5)	.029345	.14939	.19644[.846]
DLCPI(-6)	-.063952	.14312	-.44685[.659]
DLCPI(-7)	-.049037	.15298	-.32054[.751]
DLCPI(-8)	-.12535	.15970	-.78492[.441]
DLCPI(-9)	-.19994	.15458	-1.2935[.209]
DLCPI(-10)	-.24551	.16694	-1.4706[.155]
DLCPI(-11)	-.12187	.16925	-.72007[.479]
DLCPI(-12)	.73668	.17995	4.0939[.000]
LATHENSGE(-1)	-.0027179	.0036913	-.73632[.469]
LCPI(-1)	-.020348	.022821	-.89163[.382]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	3.8200[.148]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	3.9738[.137]	
F Statistic		F(2, 23)=	.95126[.401]

We can see that both statistics are outside the band suggested from Pesaran, this means that we can proceed without needing any unit root tests. In any case the unit root tests done previously both reveal the variables are I(0). We can now proceed to the next stage the long run estimates of the Error Correction Model. This is provided in table 15:

Table 15: ECM for Greece

```

Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model
      ARDL(1,0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion
*****
Dependent variable is dLATHENSGE
51 observations used for estimation from 1995M4 to 1999M6
*****
Regressor          Coefficient          Standard Error          T-Ratio[Prob]
dLCPI              .0018864              .055714                .033858[.973]
ecm(-1)          .0030568            .036769              .083136[.934]
*****
List of additional temporary variables created:
dLATHENSGE = LATHENSGE-LATHENSGE(-1)
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)
ecm = LATHENSGE + .61710*LCPI
*****
R-Squared          .0014380      R-Bar-Squared          -.018941
S.E. of Regression      .10043      F-Stat.      F( 1, 49)      .070561[.792]
Mean of Dependent Variable .031109      S.D. of Dependent Variable      .099496
Residual Sum of Squares      .49426      Equation Log-likelihood      45.8654
Akaike Info. Criterion      43.8654      Schwarz Bayesian Criterion      41.9335
DW-statistic              1.8443
*****
R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable
dLATHENSGE and in cases where the error correction model is highly
restricted, these measures could become negative.

```

We can see from the table above that the results for Greece are not in any case statistically significant indicating that our data do not explain any of the variation. The ECM term is positive- and this cannot be true-. In any case the results cannot be significant since the R^2 values are very low-even negative-. It is very obvious that a structural change taking place for Greece at the time has led to a somewhat “biasness” to the data obtained. Let us not forget that the data were taken from a highly deflationary and full of expectations for the Stock Market period based on the EMU convergence.

Hungary

The F-statistics are provided in tables 16 and 17 below:

Table 16: F-statistic for LBUX

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLBUX			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LBUX(-1)	LCPI(-1)	
32 observations used for estimation from 1996M10 to 1999M5			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	-113.5903	91.6341	-1.2396[.270]
DLBUX(-1)	-1.4021	1.2981	-1.0801[.329]
DLBUX(-2)	-1.7392	1.1699	-1.4866[.197]
DLBUX(-3)	-1.0870	1.2481	-.87089[.424]
DLBUX(-4)	-1.4312	.96476	-1.4834[.198]
DLBUX(-5)	-1.2745	1.0896	-1.1697[.295]
DLBUX(-6)	-1.8648	1.1814	-1.5784[.175]
DLBUX(-7)	-1.6709	1.3814	-1.2096[.281]
DLBUX(-8)	-2.1650	1.3672	-1.5835[.174]
DLBUX(-9)	-1.6154	1.4389	-1.1226[.313]
DLBUX(-10)	-.98169	1.0443	-.94002[.390]
DLBUX(-11)	-.41924	.72781	-.57603[.590]
DLBUX(-12)	-.26811	.53037	-.50551[.635]
DLCPI(-1)	-5.7695	14.6632	-.39347[.710]
DLCPI(-2)	.60899	8.3321	.073090[.945]
DLCPI(-3)	14.0730	8.5078	1.6541[.159]
DLCPI(-4)	-.096695	9.5957	-.010077[.992]
DLCPI(-5)	-12.1542	10.7703	-1.1285[.310]
DLCPI(-6)	-22.9747	16.1131	-1.4258[.213]
DLCPI(-7)	-22.0922	21.0482	-1.0496[.342]
DLCPI(-8)	-17.5914	21.8198	-.80621[.457]
DLCPI(-9)	-28.6477	16.9322	-1.6919[.151]
DLCPI(-10)	-20.8573	19.3159	-1.0798[.330]
DLCPI(-11)	-24.1036	15.7301	-1.5323[.186]
DLCPI(-12)	2.4307	13.6826	.17765[.866]
LBUX(-1)	.85038	.95368	.89168[.413]
LCPI(-1)	22.3233	17.5638	1.2710[.260]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 11.6360[.003]		
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 14.4629[.001]		
F Statistic	F(2, 5)= 1.4285[.323]		

Table 16: F-statistic for LCPI

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLCPI			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LBUX(-1)	LCPI(-1)	
32 observations used for estimation from 1996M10 to 1999M5			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	-3.8280	1.6943	-2.2594[.073]
DLBUX(-1)	-.071950	.024002	-2.9977[.030]
DLBUX(-2)	-.058367	.021632	-2.6982[.043]
DLBUX(-3)	-.066756	.023078	-2.8926[.034]
DLBUX(-4)	-.030973	.017838	-1.7363[.143]
DLBUX(-5)	-.038797	.020147	-1.9258[.112]
DLBUX(-6)	-.035526	.021844	-1.6264[.165]
DLBUX(-7)	-.061523	.025542	-2.4087[.061]
DLBUX(-8)	-.050317	.025279	-1.9905[.103]
DLBUX(-9)	-.074646	.026605	-2.8057[.038]
DLBUX(-10)	-.033735	.019309	-1.7471[.141]
DLBUX(-11)	-.033316	.013457	-2.4757[.056]
DLBUX(-12)	.0026557	.0098064	.27082[.797]
DLCPI(-1)	-.87322	.27112	-3.2208[.023]
DLCPI(-2)	-.41132	.15406	-2.6699[.044]
DLCPI(-3)	-.055102	.15731	-.35028[.740]
DLCPI(-4)	.51656	.17742	2.9115[.033]
DLCPI(-5)	-.043714	.19914	-.21951[.835]
DLCPI(-6)	-.33492	.29793	-1.1242[.312]
DLCPI(-7)	-1.3622	.38918	-3.5003[.017]
DLCPI(-8)	-1.0631	.40345	-2.6351[.046]
DLCPI(-9)	-.92096	.31307	-2.9417[.032]
DLCPI(-10)	-1.1100	.35715	-3.1080[.027]
DLCPI(-11)	-.89314	.29085	-3.0708[.028]
DLCPI(-12)	-1.2679	.25299	-5.0118[.004]
LBUX(-1)	.046178	.017633	2.6188[.047]
LCPI(-1)	.71688	.32475	2.2075[.078]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 19.6029[.000]		
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 30.3447[.000]		
F Statistic	F(2, 5)= 3.7531[.093]		

We can see that both values are below the critical band and as such we can proceed to the ARDL which is given below in table 17:

Table 17:ECM for Hungary

Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model			
ARDL(1,0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion			

Dependent variable is dLBUX			
33 observations used for estimation from 1996M9 to 1999M5			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
dLCPI	.32802	.13809	2.3754[.024]
ecm(-1)	-.17693	.075356	-2.3479[.025]

List of additional temporary variables created:			
dLBUX = LBUX-LBUX(-1)			
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)			
ecm = LBUX -1.8540*LCPI			

R-Squared	.15124	R-Bar-Squared	.12386
S.E. of Regression	.12234	F-Stat. F(1, 31)	5.5239[.025]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.018699	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.13070
Residual Sum of Squares	.46395	Equation Log-likelihood	23.5389
Akaike Info. Criterion	21.5389	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	20.0424
DW-statistic	1.8665		

R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable			
dLBUX and in cases where the error correction model is highly			
restricted, these measures could become negative.			

The results provided above are the best achieved so far for our dataset. Hungarian data seem to fit pretty well since the R^2 values are pretty high-even the Adjusted does not fall below the 10% mark- The ECM coefficient is statistically significant and it shows a rather moderate speed of adjustment towards equilibrium after a potential shock of the economy. The Fisher effect is still “present” in terms of sign at least since the model exhibits a positive relationship of magnitude of almost 1.85. It is very obvious from the results we have obtained so far that although there exists a relationship between inflation and stock returns this is definitely not the one suggested at least in terms of magnitude since the sign was always the one suggested by the Fisher effect, something which confirms so far the vast majority of the research on the area. We will continue the analysis on the issue by examining the empirical evidence for Israel.

The tables for the F-statistics are provided below-tables 18 and 19:

Table 18: F-statistic for LTELAV

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is LTELAV			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LTELAV(-1)	LCPI(-1)	
31 observations used for estimation from 1996M6 to 1998M12			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	-1.8013	6.3282	-.28464[.790]
DLTELAV(-1)	2.0731	.84513	2.4530[.070]
DLTELAV(-2)	2.3767	.91773	2.5898[.061]
DLTELAV(-3)	1.3029	.76061	1.7130[.162]
DLTELAV(-4)	.70218	.44953	1.5621[.193]
DLTELAV(-5)	.72087	.44940	1.6041[.184]
DLTELAV(-6)	.71216	.52289	1.3620[.245]
DLTELAV(-7)	.94091	.72920	1.2903[.266]
DLTELAV(-8)	1.4112	.77359	1.8242[.142]
DLTELAV(-9)	1.5386	.89058	1.7276[.159]
DLTELAV(-10)	1.2177	.76001	1.6022[.184]
DLTELAV(-11)	1.7228	.76235	2.2599[.087]
DLTELAV(-12)	1.0446	.76684	1.3623[.245]
DLCP(-1)	-5.8405	5.0020	-1.1676[.308]
DLCP(-2)	-6.1650	5.3949	-1.1427[.317]
DLCP(-3)	-2.2374	7.1793	-.31165[.771]
DLCP(-4)	-.96280	6.8600	-.14035[.895]
DLCP(-5)	-7.9231	6.9252	-1.1441[.316]
DLCP(-6)	-19.2567	9.8566	-1.9537[.122]
DLCP(-7)	-10.0142	10.9697	-.91290[.413]
DLCP(-8)	-16.0633	12.1698	-1.3199[.257]
DLCP(-9)	-12.5769	13.1854	-.95385[.394]
DLCP(-10)	-14.4472	11.9238	-1.2116[.292]
DLCP(-11)	-14.0423	12.8492	-1.0929[.336]
DLCP(-12)	5.6029	6.5971	.84929[.444]
LTELAV(-1)	-2.7636	1.0761	-2.5681[.062]
LCPI(-1)	3.4502	1.5097	2.2853[.084]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 20.1815[.000]		
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 32.6347[.000]		
F Statistic	F(2, 4)= 3.7309[.122]		

Table 18: F-statistic for LTELAV

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLCP			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LTELAV(-1)	LCPI(-1)	
31 observations used for estimation from 1996M6 to 1998M12			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.48401	.68194	.70976[.517]
DLTELAV(-1)	-.020071	.091073	-.22039[.836]
DLTELAV(-2)	-.058800	.098896	-.59456[.584]
DLTELAV(-3)	.0060125	.081965	.073354[.945]
DLTELAV(-4)	-.012646	.048442	-.26105[.807]
DLTELAV(-5)	.041331	.048428	.85344[.442]
DLTELAV(-6)	.087320	.056348	1.5497[.196]
DLTELAV(-7)	.020342	.078580	.25887[.809]
DLTELAV(-8)	.024967	.083364	.29949[.779]
DLTELAV(-9)	.0031760	.095971	.033093[.975]
DLTELAV(-10)	-.063374	.081901	-.77379[.482]
DLTELAV(-11)	-.049282	.082152	-.59989[.581]
DLTELAV(-12)	-.018136	.082637	-.21946[.837]
DLCP(-1)	.67599	.53903	1.2541[.278]
DLCP(-2)	-.59988	.58136	-1.0319[.360]
DLCP(-3)	-.23348	.77366	-.30179[.778]
DLCP(-4)	-.33142	.73925	-.44832[.677]
DLCP(-5)	-1.2824	.74628	-1.7184[.161]
DLCP(-6)	.39950	1.0622	.37611[.726]
DLCP(-7)	-1.2066	1.1821	-1.0207[.365]
DLCP(-8)	.79947	1.3114	.60961[.575]
DLCP(-9)	.23226	1.4209	.16346[.878]
DLCP(-10)	.33008	1.2849	.25688[.810]
DLCP(-11)	.31608	1.3847	.22827[.831]
DLCP(-12)	-.81575	.71092	-1.1475[.315]
LTELAV(-1)	-.0087993	.11597	-.075877[.943]
LCPI(-1)	-.083796	.16269	-.51505[.634]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 3.4233[.181]		
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)= 3.6275[.163]		
F Statistic	F(2, 4)= .24828[.791]		

We can see from tables 17 and 18 that both F-statistics are well below the critical range of values where the question of whether the variables are stationary or not may arise. The ECM for Israel is provided below in table 19:

Table 19:ECM for Israel

Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model			
ARDL(1,0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion			

Dependent variable is dLTELAV			
32 observations used for estimation from 1996M5 to 1998M12			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
dLCPI	.099872	.073761	1.3540[.186]
ecm(-1)	-.090503	.068399	-1.3232[.196]

List of additional temporary variables created:			
dLTELAV = LTELAV-LTELAV(-1)			
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)			
ecm = LTELAV -1.1035*LCPI			

R-Squared	.054858	R-Bar-Squared	.023353
S.E. of Regression	.054165	F-Stat. F(1, 30)	1.7413[.197]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.011606	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.054809
Residual Sum of Squares	.088016	Equation Log-likelihood	48.9295
Akaike Info. Criterion	46.9295	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	45.4638
DW-statistic	1.7414		

R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable			
dLTELAV and in cases where the error correction model is highly			
restricted, these measures could become negative.			

We can see from table 19 that the results, the coefficients of the ECM are not statistically significant and the R^2 values are not very high. Nevertheless the relationship suggested by the model between the variables is positive and of magnitude of not statistically different from 1. The Error Correction Coefficient is negative as it should be and it indicates a very modest adjustment to equilibrium after a potential shock in the economy. In this case we confirm the Fisher effect and this truly important since the Fisher relationship for Israel was always confirmed from previous empirical evidence by academics.

Mexico

The F-statistics for the significance of the lagged variables are provided in the section

below- tables 20 and 21. Table 20: F-statistic for LIPC

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLIPC			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LIPC(-1)	LCPI(-1)	
76 observations used for estimation from 1993M2 to 1999M5			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	1.6849	.59642	2.8251[.007]
DLIPC(-1)	.28906	.17535	1.6485[.106]
DLIPC(-2)	.14939	.17263	.86540[.391]
DLIPC(-3)	.31252	.19064	1.6394[.108]
DLIPC(-4)	.28445	.18529	1.5351[.131]
DLIPC(-5)	.27976	.18259	1.5322[.132]
DLIPC(-6)	.13841	.17604	.78622[.436]
DLIPC(-7)	.24709	.15414	1.6030[.115]
DLIPC(-8)	.20396	.15755	1.2946[.202]
DLIPC(-9)	.15909	.15779	1.0083[.318]
DLIPC(-10)	.39288	.16429	2.3913[.021]
DLIPC(-11)	-.096591	.16569	-.58295[.563]
DLIPC(-12)	.10973	.16258	.67493[.503]
DLCPPI(-1)	-3.4443	1.9742	-1.7447[.087]
DLCPPI(-2)	3.3142	2.6774	1.2378[.222]
DLCPPI(-3)	.67750	2.6278	.25781[.798]
DLCPPI(-4)	-.42985	2.5937	-.16573[.869]
DLCPPI(-5)	-1.5137	2.7408	-.55229[.583]
DLCPPI(-6)	-1.2954	2.8228	-.45890[.648]
DLCPPI(-7)	1.3926	2.7920	.49878[.620]
DLCPPI(-8)	-.67831	2.8117	-.24124[.810]
DLCPPI(-9)	1.3298	2.6765	.49685[.622]
DLCPPI(-10)	-2.0707	2.6804	-.77255[.443]
DLCPPI(-11)	.31126	2.6719	.11649[.908]
DLCPPI(-12)	-1.2781	2.0815	-.61401[.542]
LIPC(-1)	-.46843	.16680	-2.8083[.007]
LCPI(-1)	.41517	.15566	V2.6671[.010]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	10.7218[.005]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	11.5577[.003]	
F Statistic	F(2, 49)=	4.0241[.024]	

Table 21: F-statistic for LCPI

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLCPPI			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LIPC(-1)	LCPI(-1)	
76 observations used for estimation from 1993M2 to 1999M5			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	-.10452	.040486	-2.5816[.013]
DLIPC(-1)	-.042252	.011903	-3.5497[.001]
DLIPC(-2)	-.043427	.011718	-3.7060[.001]
DLIPC(-3)	-.040865	.012941	-3.1579[.003]
DLIPC(-4)	-.036155	.012578	-2.8744[.006]
DLIPC(-5)	-.033053	.012395	-2.6667[.010]
DLIPC(-6)	-.025559	.011950	-2.1388[.037]
DLIPC(-7)	-.024785	.010463	-2.3688[.022]
DLIPC(-8)	-.017599	.010695	-1.6456[.106]
DLIPC(-9)	-.022387	.010711	-2.0901[.042]
DLIPC(-10)	-.035769	.011153	-3.2072[.002]
DLIPC(-11)	-.025027	.011248	-2.2251[.031]
DLIPC(-12)	-.018868	.011036	-1.7096[.094]
DLCPPI(-1)	.81294	.13401	6.0662[.000]
DLCPPI(-2)	-.14978	.18175	-.82408[.414]
DLCPPI(-3)	.29259	.17838	1.6403[.107]
DLCPPI(-4)	-.41105	.17607	-2.3346[.024]
DLCPPI(-5)	.33905	.18605	1.8224[.075]
DLCPPI(-6)	-.20779	.19162	-1.0844[.283]
DLCPPI(-7)	.29177	.18953	1.5395[.130]
DLCPPI(-8)	-.10355	.19087	-.54254[.590]
DLCPPI(-9)	.22737	.18169	1.2514[.217]
DLCPPI(-10)	-.26854	.18195	-1.4759[.146]
DLCPPI(-11)	.21561	.18138	1.1888[.240]
DLCPPI(-12)	.25039	.14130	1.7721[.083]
LIPC(-1)	.034447	.011323	3.0422[.004]
LCPI(-1)	-.033698	.010567	-3.1891[.002]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	13.2252[.001]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	14.5296[.001]	
F Statistic	F(2, 49)=	5.1616[.009]	

We can see that the F-statistic for the Stock Index is inside the bounds imposed by Pesaran. Nevertheless since all the variables are I(0) and the critical value for the I(0) case is 3.793 then we can proceed with the ARDL. The ARDL is provided in table 22 below:

Table 22: ECM for Mexico

```

Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model
ARDL(1,0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion
*****
Dependent variable is dLIPC
77 observations used for estimation from 1993M1 to 1999M5
*****
Regressor          Coefficient      Standard Error    T-Ratio[Prob]
dLCPI              .080394         .047582          1.6896[.095]
ecm(-1)          -.049280         .030252         -1.6290[.108]
*****
List of additional temporary variables created:
dLIPC = LIPC-LIPC(-1)
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)
ecm = LIPC -1.6314*LCPI
*****
R-Squared          .035124      R-Bar-Squared          .022259
S.E. of Regression .095426      F-Stat.      F( 1, 75)    2.7302[.103]
Mean of Dependent Variable .014749      S.D. of Dependent Variable .096506
Residual Sum of Squares .68295      Equation Log-likelihood      72.6594
Akaike Info. Criterion 70.6594      Schwarz Bayesian Criterion      68.3156
DW-statistic      2.0946
*****
R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable
dLIPC and in cases where the error correction model is highly
restricted, these measures could become negative.

```

Our results for Mexico are not significant again since the P-values are large to consider the coefficients as statistically significant in any case. The ECM coefficient nevertheless is negative and again indicates a modest rather than rapid adjustment to equilibrium. The R^2 values can be considered as relatively low, since the data explain very little of the variation. Again the relationship between inflation and Stock returns is positive with a rather large coefficient of 1.63. in the case of Mexico again there is no evidence anyhow of the Fisher effect in terms of magnitude but the sign is always right. Again the justification of the result can be similar to the one for Chile.

Philippines

In the case of Philippines we will be using a lag of 4 instead of 12 since there are not enough observations to reliably use 12 lags. In any case there is little deviation from the analysis since the differences are statistically insignificant. The F-statistics are provided below in tables 23 and 24:

Table 23: F-statistic for LPHIL

```

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)
*****
Dependent variable is DLPHIL
List of the variables added to the regression:
LPHIL(-1) LCPI(-1)
25 observations used for estimation from 1997M6 to 1999M6
*****
Regressor      Coefficient      Standard Error      T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT         8.5623           6.0029              1.4264[.176]
DLPHIL(-1)    .50577           .25431              1.9888[.067]
DLPHIL(-2)    .27190           .29368              .92582[.370]
DLPHIL(-3)    .19958           .25501              .78262[.447]
DLPHIL(-4)    .23873           .28507              .83745[.416]
DLCPI(-1)     -4.6642          4.2421              -1.0995[.290]
DLCPI(-2)     -8.1858          4.0976              -1.9977[.066]
DLCPI(-3)     -2.8096          4.6185              -.60835[.553]
DLCPI(-4)     1.8724           4.8427              .38664[.705]
LPHIL(-1)     -.56047          .25006              -2.2413[.042]
LCPI(-1)      -.85764          .89188              -.96161[.353]
*****
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic    CHSQ( 2)= 7.9061[.019]
Likelihood Ratio Statistic        CHSQ( 2)= 9.5039[.009]
F Statistic                      F( 2, 14)= 3.2376[.070]
*****

```

Table 24: F-statistic for LCPI

```

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)
*****
Dependent variable is DLCPI
List of the variables added to the regression:
LPHIL(-1) LCPI(-1)
25 observations used for estimation from 1997M6 to 1999M6
*****
Regressor      Coefficient      Standard Error      T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT         1.0918           .30506              3.5788[.003]
DLPHIL(-1)    .033929          .012924             2.6253[.020]
DLPHIL(-2)    .030194          .014925             2.0231[.063]
DLPHIL(-3)    .036377          .012959             2.8070[.014]
DLPHIL(-4)    .032050          .014487             2.2123[.044]
DLCPI(-1)     -.39292          .21558              -1.8226[.090]
DLCPI(-2)     -.28550          .20824              -1.3710[.192]
DLCPI(-3)     -.30856          .23471              -1.3147[.210]
DLCPI(-4)     -.24078          .24610              -.97838[.344]
LPHIL(-1)     -.041640         .012708             -3.2766[.006]
LCPI(-1)      -.15471          .045324             -3.4133[.004]
*****
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic    CHSQ( 2)= 11.8791[.003]
Likelihood Ratio Statistic        CHSQ( 2)= 16.1166[.000]
F Statistic                      F( 2, 14)= 6.3375[.011]
*****

```

We can proceed to the ECM since there is no need to utilise any unit root tests to infer about the variables. The F-statistics are both outside the band imposed by the Pesaran distribution. In table 25 we provide the results of the ECM using again of course a 4 lag horizon.

Table 25: ECM for Philippines

<i>Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model</i>			
<i>ARDL(1,0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion</i>			

<i>Dependent variable is dLPHIL</i>			
<i>26 observations used for estimation from 1997M5 to 1999M6</i>			

<i>Regressor</i>	<i>Coefficient</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>T-Ratio[Prob]</i>
dLCPI	.26798	.14741	1.8179[.082]
ecm(-1)	-.17320	.095074	-1.8217[.081]

List of additional temporary variables created:			
dLPHIL = LPHIL-LPHIL(-1)			
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)			
ecm = LPHIL -1.5472*LCPI			

R-Squared	.12140	R-Bar-Squared	.084789
S.E. of Regression	.12154	F-Stat. F(1, 24)	3.3161[.081]
Mean of Dependent Variable	-.0024157	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.12705
Residual Sum of Squares	.35455	Equation Log-likelihood	18.9426
Akaike Info. Criterion	16.9426	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	15.6845
DW-statistic	1.3614		

R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable dLPHIL and in cases where the error correction model is highly restricted, these measures could become negative.			

The results provided above are statistically significant and they exhibit an ECM term of -.17320 which reveals in this case a faster adjustment than previously towards the equilibrium. The R^2 values are relatively high showing a better fit for the case of Philippines. The relationship between inflation and stock returns is for once again positive and significantly higher than 1 a result that for once again reveals the illusion of the Fisher effect at least within an emerging countries framework-in terms of magnitude always-. The next country we examine is Poland.

The F-statistics tables are provided below in tables 26 and 27:

Table 26:F-statistic for LWARSAW

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLWARSAW			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LWARSAW(-1)	LCPI(-1)	
58 observations used for estimation from 1994M7 to 1999M4			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	7.4025	4.9929	1.4826[.148]
DLWARSAW(-1)	.014319	.19827	.072222[.943]
DLWARSAW(-2)	.20685	.20122	1.0280[.312]
DLWARSAW(-3)	.25292	.19336	1.3080[.200]
DLWARSAW(-4)	.075253	.20717	.36324[.719]
DLWARSAW(-5)	.25948	.18826	1.3783[.178]
DLWARSAW(-6)	.028162	.17831	.15793[.876]
DLWARSAW(-7)	.15761	.17591	.89597[.377]
DLWARSAW(-8)	-.13264	.18723	-.70846[.484]
DLWARSAW(-9)	-.0035756	.15528	-.023027[.982]
DLWARSAW(-10)	-.4758E-3	.15770	-.0030170[.998]
DLWARSAW(-11)	.11988	.14595	.82142[.418]
DLWARSAW(-12)	-.067626	.12261	-.55157[.585]
DLCPI(-1)	3.8608	3.3401	1.1559[.257]
DLCPI(-2)	3.8347	2.0110	1.9069[.066]
DLCPI(-3)	1.6290	1.7653	.92276[.363]
DLCPI(-4)	-1.9802	1.7173	-1.1531[.258]
DLCPI(-5)	-1.8252	1.7467	-1.0449[.304]
DLCPI(-6)	.15152	1.7133	.088436[.930]
DLCPI(-7)	-.0058500	1.7078	-.0034255[.997]
DLCPI(-8)	.88459	1.6378	.54011[.593]
DLCPI(-9)	.40236	1.4627	.27509[.785]
DLCPI(-10)	.30041	1.3452	.22332[.825]
DLCPI(-11)	1.7896	1.2545	1.4265[.164]
DLCPI(-12)	-.19746	1.4032	-.14072[.889]
LWARSAW(-1)	-.26873	.17042	-1.5769[.125]
LCPI(-1)	-1.0125	.71535	-1.4153[.167]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	4.4360[.109]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	4.6148[.100]	
F Statistic		F(2, 31)=	1.2836[.291]

Table 27:F-statistic for LCPI

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is DLCPI			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	LWARSAW(-1)	LCPI(-1)	
58 observations used for estimation from 1994M7 to 1999M4			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	-.24166	.20474	-1.1803[.247]
DLWARSAW(-1)	-.0093450	.0081301	-1.1494[.259]
DLWARSAW(-2)	-.011350	.0082512	-1.3756[.179]
DLWARSAW(-3)	-.012469	.0079290	-1.5726[.126]
DLWARSAW(-4)	-.0096543	.0084951	-1.1365[.264]
DLWARSAW(-5)	.0054642	.0077198	.70782[.484]
DLWARSAW(-6)	.0028988	.0073119	.39646[.694]
DLWARSAW(-7)	-.026739	.0072132	-3.7069[.001]
DLWARSAW(-8)	-.016139	.0076773	-2.1022[.044]
DLWARSAW(-9)	.011322	.0063673	1.7781[.085]
DLWARSAW(-10)	-.0040368	.0064665	-.62427[.537]
DLWARSAW(-11)	-.0055761	.0059846	-.93173[.359]
DLWARSAW(-12)	.0084037	.0050276	1.6715[.105]
DLCPI(-1)	.45658	.13696	3.3336[.002]
DLCPI(-2)	-.16178	.082461	-1.9619[.059]
DLCPI(-3)	-.0056079	.072387	-.077470[.939]
DLCPI(-4)	.098503	.070420	1.3988[.172]
DLCPI(-5)	-.25669	.071625	-3.5838[.001]
DLCPI(-6)	-.22318	.070254	-3.1768[.003]
DLCPI(-7)	-.10529	.070030	-1.5035[.143]
DLCPI(-8)	.079116	.067159	1.1780[.248]
DLCPI(-9)	-.050548	.059978	-.84278[.406]
DLCPI(-10)	.061640	.055159	1.1175[.272]
DLCPI(-11)	-.23110	.051441	-4.4925[.000]
DLCPI(-12)	-.21654	.057539	-3.7633[.001]
LWARSAW(-1)	.0084900	.0069881	1.2149[.234]
LCPI(-1)	.032759	.029334	1.1168[.273]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	2.6661[.264]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	2.7293[.255]	
F Statistic		F(2, 31)=	.74682[.482]

We can see that both statistics are well outside the critical band, and as such we can proceed to the ADRL analysis which is provided to the next section-table 28-

Table 28:ECM for Poland

```

Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model
ARDL(1,3) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion
*****
Dependent variable is dLWARSAW
59 observations used for estimation from 1994M6 to 1999M4
*****
Regressor          Coefficient          Standard Error          T-Ratio[Prob]
dLCPI              -1.2867              1.8642                  -.69024[.493]
dLCPI1             -.72607              1.1910                  -.60961[.545]
dLCPI2             3.7243              .97181                  3.8323[.000]
ecm(-1)           -.024154            .036923                -.65416[.516]
*****
List of additional temporary variables created:
dLWARSAW = LWARSAW-LWARSAW(-1)
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)
dLCPI1 = LCPI(-1)-LCPI(-2)
dLCPI2 = LCPI(-2)-LCPI(-3)
ecm = LWARSAW -2.0530*LCPI
*****
R-Squared          .28441      R-Bar-Squared      .23140
S.E. of Regression .11572      F-Stat.    F( 3, 55)    7.1541[.000]
Mean of Dependent Variable .0040083    S.D. of Dependent Variable .13200
Residual Sum of Squares .72317      Equation Log-likelihood 46.1314
Akaike Info. Criterion 41.1314      Schwarz Bayesian Criterion 35.9376
DW-statistic 2.2412
*****
R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable
dLWARSAW and in cases where the error correction model is highly
restricted, these measures could become negative.

```

We can see from the ARDL model for the case of Poland that the included and significant variables are more than in the previous cases. The ARDL procedure decides which variables should be included in the model by itself rather than manually. As a result we can see that the fitness of data so far is the best one since the R^2 values are the highest so far. Nevertheless the ECM coefficient is not significant although it has a negative sign which is the right one and it suggests a very moderate rate of adjustment towards the equilibrium once the system has been shocked. Again the data exhibit a positive relationship between inflation and stock returns of an approximate magnitude of 2. considering the fact that Fisher was very precise in terms of the magnitude of the relationship we can say for once again that there exists a relatively weak relationship between the result above and the one suggested by Fisher.

Portugal

The F-statistics are provided below in tables 29 and 30 :

Table 29: F-statistic for L LISBO

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is <i>DLLISBO</i>			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	<i>LLISBO(-1)</i>	<i>LCPI(-1)</i>	
64 observations used for estimation from 1994M3 to 1999M6			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	-1.3489	2.5750	-.52384[.604]
DLLISBO(-1)	.16787	.16050	1.0460[.302]
DLLISBO(-2)	-.11254	.16100	-.69898[.489]
DLLISBO(-3)	.20342	.16030	1.2690[.212]
DLLISBO(-4)	-.11276	.16635	-.67785[.502]
DLLISBO(-5)	-.089397	.17134	-.52174[.605]
DLLISBO(-6)	-.046260	.15474	-.29895[.767]
DLLISBO(-7)	.19948	.14743	1.3530[.184]
DLLISBO(-8)	.14008	.14999	.93396[.356]
DLLISBO(-9)	.12975	.15661	.82849[.413]
DLLISBO(-10)	.18798	.17261	1.0891[.283]
DLLISBO(-11)	-.040559	.19123	-.21210[.833]
DLLISBO(-12)	.0073944	.18969	.038981[.969]
DLCPPI(-1)	1.0011	3.3669	.29735[.768]
DLCPPI(-2)	-.68962	3.3284	-.20719[.837]
DLCPPI(-3)	-2.9060	3.1735	-.91572[.366]
DLCPPI(-4)	-3.4409	3.2758	-1.0504[.300]
DLCPPI(-5)	-4.3504	3.1802	-1.3680[.180]
DLCPPI(-6)	1.5055	3.4149	.44088[.662]
DLCPPI(-7)	-8.0390	3.3890	-2.3721[.023]
DLCPPI(-8)	1.4540	3.4684	.41923[.677]
DLCPPI(-9)	-4.3771	3.5283	-1.2406[.223]
DLCPPI(-10)	-.69085	3.5611	-.19400[.847]
DLCPPI(-11)	-.17087	3.8490	-.044393[.965]
DLCPPI(-12)	-.45116	3.7335	-.12084[.904]
LLISBO(-1)	-.081976	.058215	-1.4082[.167]
LCPI(-1)	.43607	.63044	.69168[.493]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	5.0214[.081]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	5.2294[.073]	
F Statistic	F(2, 37)=	1.5751[.221]	

Table 30: F-statistic for LCPI

Variable Addition Test (OLS case)			
Dependent variable is <i>DLCPPI</i>			
List of the variables added to the regression:			
	<i>LLISBO(-1)</i>	<i>LCPI(-1)</i>	
63 observations used for estimation from 1994M3 to 1999M5			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	.25186	.11868	2.1222[.041]
DLLISBO(-1)	-.0065498	.0073331	-.89319[.378]
DLLISBO(-2)	-.0011318	.0073652	-.15367[.879]
DLLISBO(-3)	-.013134	.0073269	-1.7926[.081]
DLLISBO(-4)	.0086600	.0077267	1.1208[.270]
DLLISBO(-5)	-.0029706	.0078897	-.37652[.709]
DLLISBO(-6)	-.0012444	.0071135	-.17494[.862]
DLLISBO(-7)	-.0085369	.0067694	-1.2611[.215]
DLLISBO(-8)	-.0014375	.0071565	-.20087[.842]
DLLISBO(-9)	-.0024949	.0079633	-.31330[.756]
DLLISBO(-10)	-.7830E-3	.0087343	-.089643[.929]
DLLISBO(-11)	-.7514E-3	.0087545	-.085826[.932]
DLLISBO(-12)	.0075896	.0088156	.86093[.395]
DLCPPI(-1)	.14404	.15553	.92613[.361]
DLCPPI(-2)	-.20670	.15208	-1.3591[.183]
DLCPPI(-3)	-.19862	.14548	-1.3653[.181]
DLCPPI(-4)	.0056837	.15059	.037744[.970]
DLCPPI(-5)	-.31835	.14680	-2.1686[.037]
DLCPPI(-6)	.029098	.15684	.18552[.854]
DLCPPI(-7)	-.19031	.15701	-1.2121[.233]
DLCPPI(-8)	-.24298	.15861	-1.5319[.134]
DLCPPI(-9)	-.015050	.16282	-.092432[.927]
DLCPPI(-10)	-.48711	.16272	-2.9936[.005]
DLCPPI(-11)	.11906	.17588	.67695[.503]
DLCPPI(-12)	.080752	.17058	.47339[.639]
LLISBO(-1)	.0031692	.0027921	1.1351[.264]
LCPI(-1)	-.058545	.029179	-2.0064[.052]
Joint test of zero restrictions on the coefficients of additional variables:			
Lagrange Multiplier Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	8.3327[.016]	
Likelihood Ratio Statistic	CHSQ(2)=	8.9378[.011]	
F Statistic	F(2, 36)=	2.7437[.078]	

As we can see from the two tables above we can proceed to the ARDL procedure without any hesitations since the reported values of the Fstatistics are well below the critical bound imposed by Pesaran's distribution. In table 31 we present the ARDL for Portugal.

Table 31:ECM for Portugal

Error Correction Representation for the Selected ARDL Model			
ARDL(1,0) selected based on Schwarz Bayesian Criterion			
Dependent variable is dLLISBO			
64 observations used for estimation from 1994M2 to 1999M5			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
dLCPI	.013545	.032419	.41783 [.678]
ecm(-1)	-.0066619	.020622	-.32305 [.748]

List of additional temporary variables created:			
dLLISBO = LLISBO-LLISBO(-1)			
dLCPI = LCPI-LCPI(-1)			
ecm = LLISBO -2.0333*LCPI			

R-Squared	.0020709	R-Bar-Squared	-.014025
S.E. of Regression	.060401	F-Stat. F(1, 62)	.12866 [.721]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.014099	S.D. of Dependent Variable	.059982
Residual Sum of Squares	.22619	Equation Log-likelihood	89.8357
Akaike Info. Criterion	87.8357	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	85.6768
DW-statistic	1.5773		

R-Squared and R-Bar-Squared measures refer to the dependent variable			
dLLISBO and in cases where the error correction model is highly			
restricted, these measures could become negative.			

In contrast to the Polish case for Portugal the results we are getting exhibit a “bad” fit since the R^2 values are really low. The ECM coefficient is not significant statistically and it reveals a very modest adjustment towards equilibrium after a potential shock. The “Fisher” effect is not present again since we get a positive relationship once again of a value of 2. It is proven again that within an emerging countries framework at least the Fisher effect is a relatively weak, **always in terms of the size, since the sign has always been the right one** .

4.4 Conclusion

We can see that adopting the ECM method for the examination of the data has been a highly successful method. We are getting highly significant results with relative high goodness of fit compared to the ones from the OLS method. Nevertheless although we find very clear evidence that the sign of the relationship has always been the right one for the Fisher effect we cannot say the same for the magnitude for most cases. We can rather say that there exists an over adjustment for inflation for the stock returns since the coefficients have been significantly higher than 1 for most countries. Maybe for some this is not a surprise since we are dealing within an emerging countries framework and someone can expect a high risk behaviour for such portfolios which generally explains the magnitude of the relationship. In the next chapter we will examine the Fisher effect by somehow imposing it and we will also examine the cross section evidence for both long and short run data by examining monthly and semi-annual data.

Chapter V

5.1 The Fisher Effect: A further examination

The next section involves a re-examination of the long-run Fisher effect through an alternative method. In more detail we will “impose” the Fisher effect by regressing the equation below:

$$d \log SI = \mathbf{a} + \mathbf{I}_1 d \log CPI + \mathbf{I}_2 (\log SI(-1) - \log CPI(-1))$$

where the term :

$$(\log SI(-1) - \log CPI(-1))$$

represents the so called Fisher effect. The outcome of the above regression and in more detail the Sum Of the Restricted Squared Residuals will be compared with the Sum of the Unrestricted Squared Residuals of the regression below :

$$d \log SI = \mathbf{I}_1 d \log CPI + \mathbf{I}_2 ecm(-1)$$

That is of course the regression we analysed in chapter 4.

In more detail we will be comparing the respective F-statistic outlined below with the critical values of the F-distribution.

$$F - stat = \frac{SSR^R - SSR^U}{SSR^U / T - k}$$

where $T-k$ equals observations minus the degrees of freedom as indicated by the number of variables included in the regression. The decision rule will be based upon the value of the F-statistic. If the F-statistic value is higher than the respective critical value then we can confidently reject the Fisher effect hypothesis in the long run. In the table below we outline the respective F-statistics for each country and the respective decision as to whether the effect is valid:

Argentina

The reported F-statistic for Argentina is 11.3674 while the critical value is equal to 4.00. Thus we can reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level.

Brazil

The reported F-statistic for Brazil is 13.3549 while the critical value is equal to 4.08. Thus we can reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level.

Chile

The reported F-statistic for Chile is 16.77 while the critical value is equal to 4.00. Thus we can reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level.

Czech Republic

The reported F-statistic for Czech Republic is 18.82 while the critical value is equal to 4.0. Thus we can reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level.

Greece

The reported F-statistic for Greece is 5.47 while the critical value is equal to 4.00. As such we can reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level.

Hungary

The reported F-statistic for Hungary is 12.045 while the critical value is equal to 4.00. Thus we can reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level..

Indonesia

The reported F-statistic for Indonesia is 0.08 while the critical value is equal to 4.00. Thus we cannot reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level. This is a very interesting result since it shows that for the case of Indonesia the Fisher effect might be of significance

Israel

The reported F-statistic for Israel is 7.63 while the critical value is equal to 4.00

Thus we can reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level.

Mexico

The reported F-statistic for Mexico is 5.486 while the critical value is equal to 4.00

Thus we can reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level.

Philippines

The reported F-statistic for Chile is 1.69 while the critical value is equal to 4.00

Thus we cannot reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level. Another case just like the Indonesian, where the Fisher effect cannot be ignored.

Poland

The reported F-statistic for Poland is 70.55 while the critical value is equal to 4.00

Thus we can reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level.

Portugal

The reported F-statistic for Poland is 12.22 while the critical value is equal to 4.00

Thus we can reject the Hypothesis of the Long Run Fisher effect at 5% confidence level.

As we can see the above test is giving us important insights for the analysis of the phenomenon since it virtually rejects the null hypothesis of the Fisher effect in the long run in all but two cases the one for Indonesia and Philippines.

Our next test involves a short and a long run analysis of cross section data in order to derive whether the Fisher effect is identifiable among a cross section sample dataset.

5.2 Cross Section Analysis: Short and Long Run Evidence.

Below in table 1 we provide the OLS regression analysis of a cross section sample from 9 countries. After careful examination of the dataset and due to limitations in the overlapping data we have decided to pursue the analysis for a dataset starting September 1995 reaching March 1999. The countries that are not included in the analysis are : Indonesia, Philippines and Hungary.

We pursued two OLS regressions with different time horizons in order to identify possible horizons that the Fisher effect is more evident. In the first Cross section regression we consider a short time horizon and as such we used monthly data. The results are outlined below in table 1:

Table 1

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			

Dependent variable is DLSINDEX			
395 observations used for estimation from 2 to 396			

Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTERCEPT	1.1408	.10842	10.5224[.000]
D1	-.37518	1.3153	-.28525[.776]
D2	.27771	.73293	.37891[.705]
D3	-2.2101	.32471	-6.8065[.000]
D4	-3.3879	.16340	-20.7335[.000]
D5	-.0022787	.11646	-.019566[.984]
D6	-.018305	.11683	-.15668[.876]
D7	-1.2159	.19843	-6.1278[.000]
D8	-3.3203	.10604	-31.3121[.000]
DL CPI	-.21893	.15086	-1.4512[.148]

R-Squared	.95065	R-Bar-Squared	.94950
S.E. of Regression	.36379	F-Stat. F(9, 385)	824.1182[.000]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.0041568	S.D. of Dependent Variable	1.6189
Residual Sum of Squares	50.9532	Equation Log-likelihood	-156.0051
Akaike Info. Criterion	-166.0051	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	-185.8995
DW-statistic	2.9877		

Diagnostic Tests			

* Test Statistics *	LM Version	* F Version	

* A:Serial Correlation*CHSQ(1)= 98.1274[.000]*F(1, 384)= 126.9263[.000]	
* B:Functional Form *CHSQ(1)= .018920[.891]*F(1, 384)= .018394[.892]	
* C:Normality *CHSQ(2)= 1.6344[.442]*	Not applicable	
* D:Heteroscedasticity*CHSQ(1)= 18.8190[.000]*F(1, 393)= 19.6603[.000]	

We can see from the above table that although the results are statistically significant the support for the Fisher effect for a short time is very weak, in fact it is completely absent since not only our results do not indicate a relationship of 1 between inflation and stock returns but this relationship is negative with a coefficient of 0.21. Our methodology involves the inclusion of $n-1$ dummy variables, where n is the number of countries included in the analysis. The reason for that is the fact that the dummy variables do capture the effects from the different countries in the cross section analysis. The problem of heteroscedasticity naturally arises since we are dealing with a large cross section dataset. As we know from elementary econometrics there is no bias but we have two problems that we cannot simply ignore. The first is that the OLS can be inefficient and of course the second major problem is that the standard error formulae are wrong. There is a number of methods someone can utilise in order to avoid the problem of heteroscedasticity. The most evident one of course is to re-examine the equation and avoid any misspecifications. In our case the theory is very strict and this solution is not applicable. Instead we will utilise the second method which is to use the heteroscedasticity adjusted standard errors as they have been suggested by White and even better the heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation adjusted standard errors as they have been suggested by Newey and West in 1987. accordingly the appendix we provide the necessary information, the adjusted estimates for both heteroscedasticity and autocorrelation, the standard errors.

The conclusion from the above analysis is that there is not any evidence for a short term Fisher effect using cross section monthly data. We will proceed by examining, utilising exactly the same principles the six month data in order to establish whether there exists a long term Fisher effect the table below- table 2- provides the OLS estimates of the regression.

Table 2

Ordinary Least Squares Estimation			
Dependent variable is DLSINDEX			
71 observations used for estimation from 2 to 72			
Regressor	Coefficient	Standard Error	T-Ratio[Prob]
INTCPT	1.2016	.14059	8.5465[.000]
D1	-1.9214	2.8416	-.67616[.501]
D2	1.3036	1.8994	.68629[.495]
D3	-1.7429	.95218	-1.8304[.072]
D4	-3.5173	.23619	-14.8918[.000]
D6	-.17424	.19801	-.87997[.382]
D7	-1.3390	.29433	-4.5494[.000]
D8	.080290	.28258	.28413[.777]
D9	-3.4099	.20126	-16.9431[.000]
DLCPI	-.021921	.34879	-.062849[.950]
R-Squared	.94908	R-Bar-Squared	.94157
S.E. of Regression	.39596	F-Stat. F(9, 61)	126.3399[.000]
Mean of Dependent Variable	.023126	S.D. of Dependent Variable	1.6381
Residual Sum of Squares	9.5639	Equation Log-likelihood	-29.5783
Akaike Info. Criterion	-39.5783	Schwarz Bayesian Criterion	-50.8917
DW-statistic	2.8332		
Diagnostic Tests			
* Test Statistics *	LM Version	* F Version	
* A:Serial Correlation*CHSQ(1)=	13.0769[.000]	*F(1, 60)=	13.5457[.001]
* B:Functional Form *CHSQ(1)=	.0092748[.923]	*F(1, 60)=	.0078389[.930]
* C:Normality *CHSQ(2)=	.94653[.623]		Not applicable
* D:Heteroscedasticity*CHSQ(1)=	4.4338[.035]	*F(1, 69)=	4.5959[.036]

Again we find no evidence since the coefficient of the difference of the logarithm of CPI is approximately zero. Nevertheless it is very promising that by using a longer time horizon we see that the results are heading towards the Fisher effect. We are very confident that by utilising data for a much longer period and by further expanding the time horizon like for example using annual observations the coefficient will be heading towards 1 .

5.3 Final Thoughts, Conclusion

This essay is concerned with the so called Fisher effect introduced by Irvine Fisher in the early 1930's. The Fisher effect is in support of the view that there exists a positive relationship between stock returns and inflation of magnitude 1. As we examined in the introductory parts of the essay the Fisher equation, relationship is a highly debated and controversial issue in Finance. While we have seen evidence that Irvine Fisher is the "Father" of the Finance science as we know it today his views have been under attack by practitioners and academics throughout the world. Numerous pieces of work have been seen in the literature for the past 65 years challenging the topic. It is admittedly very important, and at least challenging the fact that a statement like this is still holding very much within a well respected team of academics, practitioners throughout the world. Nevertheless we were given the opportunity to examine this interesting relationship within a very different framework. It is admittedly very hard to find a piece of work related to the Fisher effect within an emerging countries framework. In any case we have attempted to examine this relationship and more interestingly we have found a conflicting piece of evidence highly restricted by the limited dataset included in the analysis. Starting the analysis from simple OLS regressions it was very evident that the lack of data almost completely eliminated any potential statistical power of the analysis. It is only natural then to find non significant results. Next we attempted to establish whether a cointegration analysis would have been more appropriate for analysing our relatively small dataset. Let us not forget that evidence of cointegration would have been very supportive for the Fisher effect. Again we found no evidence using a short time horizon for cointegration. In fact we could not even test for cointegration since the unit root tests with 12 lags did not reveal any stationarity in the data. Nevertheless we should point

out at this point that by using a short time horizon like 4 lags our dataset is a mixed bag since it is evident the existence of a unit root in the Consumer's Price Index. Considering all this the appropriate way to move onwards can only be an Autoregressive Distributed Lag approach (ARDL) to Error Correction Model (ECM) as this was suggested by Pesaran. This decision stems from the fact that such an approach is not concerned with whether the data are stationary or not but all it demanded from us was a proof for a long run relationship. This relationship was very evident from the simple tests we pursued. Continuing the analysis we found in some cases that the evidence in support of the Fisher effect in an emerging countries framework was somehow statistically significant. The important thing someone should definitely mention is the fact that in all of the cases examined-leaving aside Greece- the direction of the relationship captured by the analysis was the one suggested by Irvine Fisher. Nevertheless the magnitude, size of the relationship was not always in favour of the Fisher effect and in most cases we observed an "overshooting", attributed to a highly inflationary environment. The conclusion from this important part of our research was conflicting. We definitely needed something stronger statistically in order to examine the relationship in question. The next part of our research involved a comparison of the residuals involving an F-statistic. In more detail we somehow imposed the Fisher effect and we compared the residuals with the ECM. In almost all of the cases at 5% significance we could reject the possibility of a long run existence of the Fisher effect- with the exception of Indonesia and Philippines- . The scale now is moving definitely towards against supporting the examined relationship. The final part of our analysis involved two large cross section regressions. In these two regressions we examined the possibility of the Fisher effect but the results were disappointingly against the "effect" especially in the short run.

We have left our last hopes for a long horizon analysis. We simply hoped to establish what other researchers established previously, the fact that there exists a “thing” called Fisher effect but only in the long run. Again the actual numbers were disappointing, but nevertheless the fact that the coefficient was moving towards the support of the Fisher effect was clearly showing us that we were targeting to the right direction. Again the statistical limitations of the dataset and in more detail of the small dataset are very obvious. The next logical step we would have followed is to examine the data on an annual basis. This would have definitely revealed a relationship towards the one suggested by Fisher.

In conclusion we cannot establish whether the Fisher effect “exists” or not within an emerging countries framework at least. We are in “desperate” need of a larger dataset to establish that. If we definitely wanted a closing statement we could only say that in the short run the evidence is definitely against while examining the data in a longer time horizon looks at least promising.

APPENDIX

Newey-White Adjusted Standard Errors and Coefficient of 1 month Cross Section

Regression.

Estimated Variance-Covariance Matrix of parameters Adjusted White's Heteroscedasticity-Consistent Estimates Based on OLS regression of DLSINDEX on:				
INTERCEPT	D1	D2	D3	D4
D5	D6	D7	D8	
DLCPI				
395 observations used for estimation from 2 to 396				
INTERCEPT	D1	D2	D3	D4

INTERCEPT	.0080639	-.10629	.057951	
.024920				
D1	-.10629	1.5154	-.83691	-
.36494				
D2	.057951	-.83691	.46746	
.20363				
D3	.024920	-.36494	.20363	
.092981				
D4	-.012130	.16437	-.090193	-
.038993				
D5	-.0079162	.10408	-.056727	-
.024374				
D6	-.0076534	.10040	-.054684	-
.023491				
D7	-.016942	.23270	-.12813	-
.055500				
D8	-.0060950	.078220	-.042372	-
.018128				
DLCPI	.012118	-.17314	.096111	
.041953				

	D4	D5	D6	D7
INTERCEPT .016942	-.012130	-.0079162	-.0076534	-
D1 .23270	.16437	.10408	.10040	
D2 .12813	-.090193	-.056727	-.054684	-
D3 .055500	-.038993	-.024374	-.023491	-
D4 .025870	.018811	.011896	.011492	
D5 .016523	.011896	.014314	.0075101	
D6 .016020	.011492	.0075101	.010715	
D7 .038037	.025870	.016523	.016020	
D8 .012680	.0090811	.0060016	.0057968	
DLCPI .026628	-.018783	-.011866	-.011443	-

	D8	DLCPI
INTERCEPT	-.0060950	.012118
D1	.078220	-.17314
D2	-.042372	.096111
D3	-.018128	.041953
D4	.0090811	-.018783
D5	.0060016	-.011866
D6	.0057968	-.011443
D7	.012680	-.026628
D8	.0074356	-.0088974
DLCPI	-.0088974	.019867

*Newey-White Adjusted Standard Errors and Coefficient of 6 month Cross Section
Regression.*

```

Estimated Variance-Covariance Matrix of parameters
Adjusted White's Heteroscedasticity-Consistent Estimates
Based on OLS regression of LSINDEX on:
INTCPT      D1      D2      D3      D4
D6           D7      D8      D9      DLCPI
71 observations used for estimation from 2 to 72
*****
INTCPT      D1      D2      D3      D4
.021731     .034084  -.070966  -.0093387  -
D1          2.9133  -.070966  8.9909    -5.9103    -
D2          1.9918  -.0093387  -5.9103    4.0013
D3          1.0092  -.021731  -2.9133    1.9918
D4          .097624  -.035582  .43333    -.23137    -
D6          .097094  -.033057  -.15825    .16200
D7          .20674  -.036976  .76472    -.45163    -
D8          .27279  -.030891  -.69145    .51601
D9          .065764  -.033540  -.062672  .098068
DLCPI      .36273  .0045581  -1.1013    .73159
*****

```

	D4	D6	D7	D8
INTCPT .030891	-.035582	-.033057	-.036976	-
D1 .69145	.43333	-.15825	.76472	-
D2 .51601	-.23137	.16200	-.45163	
D3 .27279	-.097624	.097094	-.20674	
D4 .0014823	.054848	.025206	.066586	
D6 .047703	.025206	.076069	.019116	
D7 .024882	.066586	.019116	.10391	-
D8 .099280	.0014823	.047703	-.024882	
D9 .041938	.029634	.036366	.025957	
DLCPI .089276	-.049156	.023651	-.089942	

	D9	DLCPI
INTCPT	-.033540	.0045581
D1	-.062672	-1.1013
D2	.098068	.73159
D3	.065764	.36273
D4	.029634	-.049156
D6	.036366	.023651
D7	.025957	-.089942
D8	.041938	.089276
D9	.059222	.011890
DLCPI	.011890	.13554

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